

Proceedings of the Conference on Geotechnical Engineering for Renewable Energy

Organised by the Geotechnical Society of Ireland

The Midlands Park Hotel
Portlaoise, Co Laois, Ireland

Wednesday, 19th October 2022

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Edited by:

Carl Brangan (ESB)

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Ciaran Reilly (Ciaran Reilly & Associates)

Susan Stack (ESB)

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Table of Contents

Introduction	III
Committees	V
<i>Invited Papers</i>	
Foundations for solar farms <i>R. Kelly</i>	3
Research into practice in offshore renewables <i>K. Gavin</i>	13
Geothermal Energy (GE); Unrealised remedy for climate action? <i>S. Finlay</i>	21
<i>Offshore and Onshore Wind</i>	
An overview and benefits of ground improvement for gravity-based wind turbine foundation design and construction <i>K. Coghlan, C. Plomteux, J. Flannery, J. Racinais</i>	29
Comparison of geotechnical design criteria for offshore monopiles <i>D. Igoe, L. Lapastoure & S. Jalilvand</i>	37
Review of cyclic models for the design of monopiles supporting offshore wind turbines <i>L. Lapastoure, S. Jalilvand, A. Diambra & D. Igoe</i>	43
Use of shear wave velocity (V_s) to characterise offshore glacial tills <i>M. Long & M. Coughlan</i>	53
Innovative weather downtime assessment tool (WDAT) for offshore operations <i>B. Schira, H. Kustura, G. Shoukat & I. Thusyanthan</i>	63
A novel approach to offshore site investigation using Distributed Acoustic Sensing <i>A. Trafford, R. Ellwood, A. Godfrey, C. Minto, M. Coughlan & S. Donohue</i>	71
A review of anchoring solutions for offshore wind turbines <i>R. Varghese, V. Pakrashi & D. Igoe</i>	79

Introduction

On behalf of Engineers Ireland and the Geotechnical Society of Ireland, I am delighted to welcome you to this conference on Geotechnical Engineering for Renewable Energy. This is the fifth in a series of conferences that have been organised by the Geotechnical Society of Ireland, with previous events held in 1996, 2007, 2012 and 2017 on themes that have included the geotechnical engineering of soft ground, road construction, and ground and surface water.

When the committee of the Geotechnical Society of Ireland started planning our 2022 conference we alighted on our topic almost immediately. Given the challenges that are ahead of us as we aim for Net Zero Emissions, the theme of Geotechnical Engineering for Renewable Energy was a very popular choice.

We are very grateful to all of the authors who have taken the time to write papers and share their knowledge and experiences. In the last twenty years, a complete transformation has occurred in power generation, with a significant portion of our energy now provided by onshore wind. Novel techniques are still being found to construct even larger turbines. We have also had huge support from researchers looking at the various challenges posed by offshore wind development on our coasts. This is the single most important development in the move to Net Zero and we appreciate that they have taken time to share their work on foundation design and seabed ground investigation.

We are particularly grateful to our invited speakers, Dr Richard Kelly of SMEC, Dr Ken Gavin of TU Delft, and Sean Finlay of Geoscience Ireland. They have been able to widen the discussion to other areas of renewable energy. Solar energy is still at its infancy in Ireland and Richard Kelly's experiences of developments in Australia are hugely instructive. Ken Gavin is well-known in the context of Irish offshore research and he has provided an inciteful summary of the research in that field. Much of our focus at the conference is on electricity generation and Sean Finlay brings a wealth of knowledge on a different aspect of renewable energy, geothermal energy. This is another largely untapped resource that will allow the nation to achieve its climate goals.

We would also like to thank Henry Bouchier of ESB for introducing our event and to Tanya Keyes of ESB Archives who provided a special presentation on the history of two of Ireland's first renewable electricity projects, the Shannon Scheme and Turlough Hill. ESB has provided great support for this event and I would like to thank all of my colleagues for their assistance.

We are hugely grateful to all of our sponsors for their support. They come from various companies involved in civil engineering and geotechnical engineering providing materials supply, consultancy services, and contracting services. Their support of the event helps the Society promote geotechnical engineering in Ireland and allows us to sponsor young geotechnical engineers to attend international events.

We are really pleased that we have been able to host this event in Portlaoise in "the old fashioned way". I am saying nothing novel by observing that the last two years have been challenging. We are delighted that so many people have chosen to attend and that we will all see faces that we have not seen in a long time. We thank you all for attending.

Finally, I'm very grateful to my colleagues from the Geotechnical Society of Ireland; Dr David Igoe (Trinity College Dublin), Dr Kevin Flynn (Brazil Piling and Foundations), Dr Juan Pablo Osorio Salas (TU Dublin), Dr Ciaran Reilly (Ciaran Reilly & Associates), and Susan Stack (ESB), and to Engineers Ireland, in particular Elva O'Doherty and Amanda Greville, for their considerable efforts in putting today's event together. I hope you find this to be an informative and an enjoyable day. Thank you for your support.

*Dr Carl Brangan, ESB Engineering & Major Projects
Chartered Engineer, Engineers Ireland
Chairperson, Geotechnical Society of Ireland.*

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Invited Papers

Foundations for Solar Farms

Richard Kelly¹

¹Chief Technical Principal for Geotechnical Engineering and General Manager Technical Excellence, SMEC, Australia

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ABSTRACT: The large scale development of utility scale solar farms in Australia has meant that the effects of near surface ground conditions on the performance of piled foundations needs to be understood. Estimating the depth of wetting and drying at the time the ultimate wind loading event occurs is needed for pile design. Estimating fluctuations in ground movement as a result of rainfall and evaporation is required to assess serviceability conditions. Methods to assess their behaviour such as the use of unsaturated soil mechanics and stochastic calculations are in their relative infancy, at least for practicing engineers. Various issues and uncertainties arising from the need to optimise solar farm foundations are discussed in this paper. Despite these uncertainties, the greatest risk to solar farm foundations is refusal above founding level during installation. Somewhat counterintuitively, conservative design leading to longer piles can increase project risk.

KEY WORDS: Solar farm, pile foundation, unsaturated soils, stochastic methods

1 INTRODUCTION

Utility-scale solar farms have been constructed in Australia since about 2016. The solar arrays have typically been either fixed tilt or tracking arrays supported on pile foundations that double as a supporting cantilever post for the solar panels. One of the design considerations is how the foundations behave in reactive soils. In 2015, a literature study found design procedures aimed to limit movements of masonry buildings and light industrial structures (eg Chen, 1975). These procedures design piles to be below the active depth of soil movement to resist the uplift loads. In Australia, that meant that piles were being designed 4m to 6m below ground level which (a) are expensive (b) are longer than international experience in 2015 in North America in particular and (c) run the risk of refusing during installation prior to founding depth being achieved. These designs were not economic or practical and refinement was required.

Refinement came from the realisation that solar arrays are very flexible structures and can accommodate movement. Therefore the piles were designed to move and their lengths below ground in cohesive soils reduced to a range in the order of 1.5m to 2.5m.

Designing piles to move is a novel concept. Usually piles are adopted to prevent something from moving. Further, if piles are designed to move then the magnitude of that movement needs to be calculated. In order to do this, the response of near surface soils to changes in environmental conditions needs to be understood. Moreover, wind loads drive lateral foundation movement and ultimate pile capacity. The pile movements and capacity are a function of the strength and stiffness of the ground hence its moisture content. That begs a question of how to quantify what the ground moisture will be when the wind blows? Or, has it rained for a period of time, hence how deep into the ground is the moisture affected zone, before the ultimate wind event occurs? Ground investigations and pile testing occur at a point in time. An engineer needs to estimate what the ground conditions will be when the ultimate or serviceability loading events occur. At the moment, engineering judgement is used to assess what the ground conditions could be in the future. Potential developments are the adoption of unsaturated soil mechanics, stochastic methods to estimate probabilities of wind and rain events, understanding the behaviour of near surface soils in more detail, more accurate quantification of rates of steel and zinc corrosion and adopting structural reliability assessments for structural and geotechnical pile capacity.

The behaviour of near surface soils, use of unsaturated soil and probabilistic methods are all areas in their relative infancy, at least for practicing engineers. Issues arising from the need to optimise solar farm foundations are discussed in this paper with the aim of raising more questions than providing answers.

2 UTILITY SCALE SOLAR FARMS

In Australia 21GW of solar farms was constructed between 2001 and 2021. Typically the solar farms are located in near proximity to transmission lines, shown in Figure 1, in order to facilitate connection into the grid.

Figure 1. Locations of solar farms (yellow dots) adjacent to transmission lines (red lines)

Utility scale solar farms are large, occupying 4Ha to 6Ha per megawatt capacity. Figure 2 shows that a typical 250MW solar farm occupies a space similar to the Brisbane CBD. Figure 3 shows that a 10GW solar farm occupies a space similar to the entire city of Brisbane. A 40GW solar farm is currently being planned in the Northern Territory.

As a rough rule of thumb, there is about 1 pile per 2kW of capacity. Therefore there will be about 125,000 piles in a 250MW solar farm and about 5,000,000 piles in a 10GW solar farm. The material cost of typical galvanised H piles is about \$90AUD per pile and installation cost is about \$30AUD per pile. Obviously, design refinement can lead to substantial cost savings.

Figure 2. Relative size of a 250MW solar farm

Figure 3. Relative size of a 10GW solar farm

Ideally solar farms are located in a flat area that has a few metres of cohesive soil cover in order to minimise earthworks and enable driven piles to be used. Most of these sites have

been used to date and more undulating sites with less soil cover are becoming more common. This increases earthworks and can lead to the need to bore piles rather than drive them, both of which increases cost.

A typical solar array is shown in Figure 4. The solar panels are attached to a torque tube which is in turn attached to the piles. A motor will be located somewhere along the array or between the arrays which turns the panels to follow the sun. The NEXTracker XTR system is shown in Figure 5. This system is designed to follow the ground contours in order to minimise earthworks. The image also demonstrates that the arrays are highly flexible and do not need to be straight to operate. Images of solar farms are shown in Figures 6 and 7. The solar farm shown in Figure 7 mixes land use to farm sheep (and kangaroos!). Mixed land use is probably a trend that will accelerate into the future.

Figure 4. Typical solar array (courtesy NEXTracker)

Figure 5. XTR solar array (courtesy NEXTracker)

Figure 6. Typical solar farm (courtesy NEXTracker)

Figure 7. Mixed use solar farm (courtesy NEXTracker)

3 NEAR SURFACE GROUND CONDITIONS

Near surface ground conditions can vary considerably from site to site. A typical reactive clay is shown in Figure 8. These soils shrink and swell. When dry, they crack sometimes to several metres depth but also stiffen and strengthen. Gilgais (water filled depressions) and crab holes form in the more highly reactive terrains which are shown in Figures 9 and 10.

Figure 8. Reactive clay soils

Figure 9. Gilgai

Figure 11. Sandy soil sites

Figure 10. Crab hole

Figure 12. Flooded site

A sandy soil site is shown in Figure 11. Sands have little strength near surface where the effective stress is low and the piles are typically longer in length than in cohesive soils.

Flooding and erosion can be an issue on some sites, examples of which are shown in Figures 12 and 13.

Obstructions during pile driving are a major issue on some sites, particularly those in basalt or granite terrain where corestones and boulders can be present. An example of boulders in a granite terrain is shown in Figure 14.

Figure 13. Eroded site

Figure 14. Boulders in a granite terrain

4 DESIGN CRITERIA, LOADS AND LOAD CASES

A typical pile will be subject to horizontal and vertical components of wind load and soil movements. Motor piles will also have a torque applied at the pile head.

Figure 15. Pile loading

The maximum wind speed is identified for a given geographic location, return period and structure importance class. Most solar array providers have performed wind tunnel testing to generate pressure coefficients to convert wind speed into top of post loads.

The piles need to be designed for ultimate structural and geotechnical capacity and for serviceability displacements. There are no absolute limits to pile movement provided by the suppliers. Lateral or vertical differential movements between

posts need to be kept to within 25mm to 50mm depending on the adopted system. The posts are typically spaced at 6m to 8m centres so the differential movement allowance is relatively large.

The two ultimate limit state failure modes typically assessed are the lateral-torsional capacity of the pile and the lateral geotechnical capacity of the pile. Axial pullout is typically not the critical mechanism of failure. The structural capacity of the pile depends on the effective length to maximum bending moment and this length can be below ground level. The geotechnical capacity of the pile depends on the length of the pile into the ground. Both lengths are a function of the strength of the ground.

Cohesive soil loses strength when it is wet and gains strength when it is dried, albeit cracking is possible to several metres depth around the pile in very dry soils. What combination of wetting and drying should be adopted by an engineer for the ultimate limit state calculation? There is no guidance in Australian standards and engineering judgement is required. The Australian Standard for residential slabs and footings has a method to assess wet and dry profiles to depth and is often used to estimate soil movements. Notionally, the profiles provided in the standard imply a 5% probability of exceedance. If this is combined with a 1% exceedance wind event is that too conservative? Further, some areas of Australia are arid where evaporation generally exceeds rainfall while in other areas it is more likely that rainfall could exceed evaporation. Moreover, wind speed and rainfall do not appear to be strongly correlated where assessed by the author, for example Figure 16. Despite this, the author's judgement is that some affect of rain on soil strength should be adopted in a design; the problem is assessing just how much and to what depth.

Figure 16. Daily wind and rain in Newcastle, Australia

5 WETTING, DRYING AND PILE CAPACITY

A photograph of structural failure at a solar farm is shown in Figure 17. Experience at various sites indicates that most piles buckle either at surface or a few hundred millimetres below ground surface. Piles buckle before failing geotechnically, although some piles may have displaced beyond serviceability limits.

Lee *et al.* (2019) investigated the problem shown in Figure 18 using three dimensional structural finite element analysis and generated a nomograph shown in Figure 19 to assess the depth below ground where a pile might buckle. A ratio of 1 indicates buckling at the ground surface. A ratio greater than

1 indicates the effective length to the depth of buckling is greater than the length of pile above the ground surface. Piles will buckle at the ground surface if they are relatively flexible compared with the stiffness of the ground but buckle below surface where the ground is soft or the piles are stiff.

Figure 17. Structural failure at a solar farm

Figure 2a

Figure 2b

Figure 18. Lateral torsional structural mechanism (Lee *et al.*, 2019)

Figure 19. Nomograph of effective lengths of pile (Lee *et al.*, 2019)

Load-displacement plots for pile load tests performed in dry conditions after 5 days of simulated wetting are shown in Figure 20. Dynamic cone penetration tests indicated that the ground had softened to about 1m depth. Results of the testing (Site 8) shows a softer load-displacement response than for the dry test, albeit that the embedded pile lengths were not identical.

Figure 20. Load displacement tests for dry (royal blue) and wet tests (orange)

Axial and lateral pile tests have also been performed in very dry, cracked soils. The piles were installed to 1.2m and 1.4m depth. In these dry cracked soils, most of the axial load tests passed the test load whereas most of the lateral load tests failed to pass the test deformation criterion (but would have large ultimate lateral capacity).

6 WETTING, DRYING AND PILE MOVEMENTS

There is an ongoing debate in Australia regarding effects of soil shrinking and swelling on the axial movement of piles and whether piles will ratchet out of the ground over time. The movement of a pile can be estimated as a function of soil surface swelling and pile length (L) relative to the active zone (Z_a) using solutions shown in Figures 21 and 22. In these figures data from field trials reported by Cameron and Walsh (1981) and Fityus and Delaney (2001) are compared with theoretical solutions. Correlation between measurement and theory is acceptable, particularly for the case of linearly increasing uplift with depth.

Pile head movements recorded over about 18 months by Fityus and Delaney (2001) and 3 years by Cameron and Walsh (1981) are shown in Figures 23 and 24. Both sets of data show the majority of the movement occurred in the first year with much less cyclic movement occurring in subsequent years. Questions arising from these observations are: (1) is it reasonable to assume the majority of movement will only occur in the first year?; (2) is 18 months to 3 years a long enough record to be reliable?; and (3) why would pile movement be suppressed after the first year?

While these questions are unresolved, there is some indication in the technical literature that ground conditions stabilise over time. Kodikara *et al.* (2002) discuss "soil ripening" which is a process of soils forming stable structures over a period of wetting and drying cycles. In addition there are a number of laboratory studies which show that swelling pressures in 1D oedometer tests reduce progressively with the

number of wetting and drying cycles, for example Rosenbalm and Zapata (2017).

Kelly *et al.* (2021) developed a method to estimate pile head movements over time by combining elements of unsaturated soil mechanics with rainfall records, Monte-Carlo simulations and numerical analysis of pile response to soil movements. Results of the simulations (Figure 25) show that the distribution of pile movements is wider when piles are shorter and narrower when piles are deeper. All distributions are relatively evenly spread around zero pile movement for the various assumptions made in this assessment.

Figure 21. Pile head movement using elastic solutions (Kelly 2021 based on Poulos and Davis, 1980)

Figure 22. Pile head movement (Kelly *et al.* 2021 based on Nelson *et al.* 2007))

Figure 23. Pile head movement (Fityus and Delaney, 2021)

Figure 24. Pile head movement (Cameron and Walsh, 1981)

Figure 25. Pile head movement (Kelly, 2021)

7 STRUCTURAL RELIABILITY IN DESIGN

Pile foundations are sized, and usually galvanised, to resist corrosion so that the design factor of safety is achieved on the last day of operation. That means that the actual factor of safety throughout the life of the project is greater than required by the standards. The asset owner pays for that level of reliability through increased material costs. At the end of life (25 to 35 years) the installation will be bulldozed because technology will have advanced to the point where salvage is uneconomic. The waste materials will be either recycled or put into landfill. Those observations raise a question whether it is more economic and sustainable to design to a probability of structural failure to reduce materials and costs?

Kelly *et al.* (2021) reports a preliminary structural reliability assessment where the probability of lateral-torsional buckling of a heavier (W6x8.5) and lighter (W6x7) pile were compared over the lifetime of a project. The probabilities of failure are compared in Figure 26. A normal structural calculation was done to adopt the W6x8.5 piles for the conditions assumed in this case. These probabilities of failure are therefore consistent with current Australian design standards. Probabilities of failure are higher for the W6x7 section but are still relatively low. An economic analysis comparing reductions in capital cost with potential increases in maintenance cost would be required to assess whether or not it is better to adopt the lighter section.

Figure 26. Probabilities of failure for two section sizes (Kelly *et al.*, 2021)

8 PILE INSTALLATION

Despite the various sources of uncertainty discussed in the preceding sections, the number one risk by far is pile refusal during installation. There have been several instances where millions of dollars have been spent remediating the effects of pile refusal.

Piles are typically driven and sometimes bored (plus some other systems used sporadically such as blade piles). Refusals typically occur on obstructions and in hard ground. Removal of piles, pre-boring or testing and acceptance can be done as remedial works but are expensive and time-consuming exercises. Even if piles are tested and accepted at higher than founding level, they still need to be cut off to top of pile level and new holes drilled for connection to the torque tubes.

Cut earthworks reduces the distance from surface level to harder materials. Sometimes pile design is based on site investigation levels rather than final earthworks level due to the piling being procured separately from the civil design. As a result there can be less soil than anticipated leading to pile refusals.

Engineered fill often has lower capacity than natural ground and this can require greater width and depth of foundations to resist lateral loads.

Conservative design (i.e. longer piles) also increases the risk of pile refusal.

Out-of-tolerance installation, or installation at the limits of tolerance, can lead to exceedances of differential tolerances between piles if a small amount of ground movement occurs. Installing piles as accurately as possible to tolerance avoids this risk and facilitates construction of the solar array.

9 CONCLUDING REMARKS

The near surface soil behaviour that is important for the design of solar farms requires engineers to consider different mechanisms than in the past. Effects of wetting and drying on the strength and serviceability of piled foundations are key elements along with the probability that the wind will blow when the ground is wet.

Currently engineering judgement is used to estimate ground conditions at the time of an ultimate wind event. Future developments using unsaturated soil mechanics and stochastic methods promise a method to quantify performance.

Ground and pile movements fluctuate with rainfall and evaporation, are typically small and only large a few times over the design life. These movements can be estimated using simple methods or more complex stochastic methods.

Structural reliability methods potentially enable significant cost savings but more work is required to achieve the rigour that an asset owner or insurer would need to confidently adopt this approach.

There are many uncertainties that require use of engineering judgement such as depth of wetting and whether soil ripening occurs. Despite these uncertainties, refusal during installation is the biggest risk for a project. Ground conditions and earthworks design levels need to be assessed. Conservative design of longer piles aimed at controlling the effects of ground movements on pile movements increases this risk. Sometimes adoption of shorter piles reduces project risk, which can be a counter-intuitive concept.

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Research into Practice in Offshore Renewables

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ABSTRACT: Given the increased need to develop alternative, clean energy sources the paper presents details of recent and ongoing R&D programmes with a focus on reducing costs offshore developments and increasing safety. Collaborative research projects conducted by industry and academia have delivered significant cost savings for offshore renewables projects. Work on the development of design codes for both laterally and axially loaded large diameter piles is presented. The new design methodologies provide reliable predictions of monotonic loading. Remaining challenges such as quantifying the impact of cyclic loading, accurate prediction of installation resistance and minimisation of environmental impact still require fundamental understanding. New areas of research are highlighted in particular problem soils and foundations for floating installation.

KEY WORDS: Research and Development, Pile Foundations.

1 INTRODUCTION

Across the globe governments are setting very ambitious targets for energy generation from offshore renewable sources. Fixed bottom and floating offshore wind farms are seen as key to achieving this aim. Siting turbines offshore provide several benefits including: (i) the availability of high unrestricted wind speeds, (ii) the ability to use larger turbines, (iii) the ability to develop combined wind and wave/solar energy installations and (iv) the potential for offshore hydrogen production.

The first and second parts of the paper summarise recently completed R&D projects focused on the development of new design codes for laterally loaded and axially loaded piles respectively. Ongoing research topics related to these developments are addressed in Section 4. In the final section issues related to new challenges, including reducing the environmental impact of piling, challenging soil and loading conditions are discussed.

2 PISA DESIGN METHODOLOGY FOR MONOPILES

2.1 Background

The PISA (Pile Soil Analysis) project was a Joint Industry Project, JIP established to develop new design methods for the very large diameter, relatively rigid monopiles used to support offshore wind turbines. The project involved: (i) field testing at two separate sites, dense sand at Dunkirk and stiff clay at Cowden; (ii) numerical modelling using 3D finite element analysis; and (iii) the development of a new design method. The work was directed by an Academic Work Group (AWG), led by the University of Oxford and comprising researchers from Imperial College (IC) and University College Dublin (UCD) latterly Technical University Delft (TUD) in collaboration with the Geotechnical Consulting Group and supported by the larger PISA industrial consortium. The main technical outputs of the project summarised in a freely available special issue of *Géotechnique* <https://www.icvirtuallibrary.com/toc/jgeot/70/11>.

2.2 Field work

The major field test programme undertaken at the two sites was performed between October 2014 and July 2015. The work summarised below is described in detail by Byrne et al. (2020) and McAdam et al. (2020). The field tests were performed in an onshore setting to allow for multiple tests to be performed that investigate a range of the parameters that govern pile performance and to investigate the effects of scale. In total there were 14 test piles at each site. Three pile diameters were tested, 0.273m, 0.762m and 2m. The majority of tests were performed on the mid-size 0.762m diameter piles.

Load tests were carried out as a series of maintained load steps, which targeted specific displacements and included a main unload-reload loop after the third load step. A limited number of additional load tests were performed to explore rate effects, cyclic loading and damping. The test piles were loaded at a height h , above ground level of between 5 and 10m in order to consider normalised Moment, M , horizontal load, H , and pile diameter, D , ratios representative of those arising from wind and wave loads applied to offshore wind

turbines. The piles were instrumented with fibre optic strain gauges, inclinometers and extensometers in the buried section (piezometers were placed in the soil at Cowden). In addition above ground instruments included inclinometers, LVDTs and load cells, See Figure 1.

Figure 27. Fully instrumented 762mm diameter PISA pile at Cowden (Burd et al. 2020)

A comparison of the impact of normalised pile penetration depth (L/D - the pile penetration depth, L normalised by the pile diameter, D) on the load-displacement response of 762mm diameter piles tested at Dunkirk is shown in Figure 2. The pile capacity and stiffness increased significant as L/D increased.

Figure 2. Comparison of load-displacement response of pile with varying L/D (McAdam et al. 2020)

Significant rate effects that were recorded in tests on piles installed in stiff glacial till at Cowden were expected. The effect of the rate of loading on the load-displacement response of a 762mm diameter with L/D of 5.25 installed in dense marine sand at Dunkirk is considered in Figure 3. The first four-load steps were conducted using the standard monotonic

loading regime. The pile was then loaded at a varying rates (from a minimum of 0.45mm/min to a maximum of 330mm/minute). An interesting feature of the response is that it appears a unique backbone curves exists for each load rate, with the pile resistance increasing as the loading rate increased.

Figure 3. Consideration of rate effects for 762mm diameter pile with L/D = 5.25 at Dunkirk (McAdam et al. 2020)

2.3 Design Approach

The PISA design model builds on the old industry-standard p-y method and includes additional soil reaction components, namely; vertical shear stresses at the pile-soil interface, horizontal force and moment at the pile base, See Figure 4. These components become increasingly important as L/D reduces.

Figure 4 Soil reaction components of a rigid monopile (Byrne et al. 2020)

The component soil reaction curves can be determined from either a simplified rules-based method or a more comprehensive numerical method described in Byrne et al. (2019).

3 UNIFIED CPT METHOD FOR THE AXIALLY LOADED PILES IN SAND

3.1 Background

The axially capacity of offshore (typically open-ended piles) has been an area of significant research interest in recent years. Methods developed primarily for the offshore oil and gas industry adopted traditional earth pressure theory. Focussed research in the 1990s led to updated design codes API (2007) and DNV (2007, 2011) that maintained the traditional design methodology as the main text approach whilst allowing the use of any one of four alternative Cone Penetration Test (CPT) methods for estimating pile resistance in sand. These methods named after the organisations that led their development were known as the Fugro-05, NGI-05, ICP-05 and UWA-05 methods. Comprehensive database studies reported by Chow (1997) and Schneider et al. (2008) revealed that the CPT based methods were more reliable than earth pressure based approaches. Gavin et al. (2013) compared the predictive capacity of the methods for estimating the tension shaft resistance developed by open-ended piles in sand. In total, seventeen load tests were collated from eleven sites. The shaft capacity calculated using the design methods ($Q_{\text{predicted}}$) are compared to values measured in static load tests (Q_{measured}) in Figure 5. Included in Figure 5 is the estimated un-factored pull-out force for a corner pile in 4-pile jacket supporting a 5 MW turbine.

Figure 5 Comparison of predictive performance of various design approaches for a database of open-ended pile tests (Gavin et al. 2013)

The data in Figure 5 suggest that most design methods worked reasonably well at predicting pile capacities below 5MN. However, as the applied vertical load increased towards the expected design load for a 5MW turbine, all methods

significantly under-estimated the measured resistance. No field test data existed to validate the models for loads in excess of the expected design load. Gavin et al. (2013) then used synthetic soil profiles to assess the effect of pile geometry on the capacity predicted by the various CPT based design approaches. This simple study suggested that empirical factors introduced in each of the methods to account for differences between open and closed-ended pile behaviour caused bias in the predictions that was not apparent from the database study in Figure 5.

A JIP was established to examine the reliability of the CPT based methods using a much larger unified dataset of load tests on driven piles in sand, Lehane et al. (2017). A follow-up project brought together representatives of the four organisations that developed the alternative CPT methods to produce a single design method calibrated against the database of pile tests. As a result the forthcoming 2022 version of the ISO-19901-4 guidelines includes only the unified method, described by Lehane et al. (2020). The method incorporates physical mechanisms observed in load tests on highly-instrumented piles that are seen to control the shaft and base resistance of displacement piles in sand.

3.2 Shaft Resistance

Important insights into the effective stress response of closed-ended displacement piles installed in sand have been provided by tests performed using the Imperial College Pile, ICP. Key to these insights were measurements from the radial and shear stress sensors fitted at a number of discrete locations along the pile shaft. The ICP was installed and tested at a loose to medium-dense sand at Labenne and also in a dense sand deposit at Dunkirk (Chow 1997).

The local shear stress τ_f measured by three sensors during the jacked installation of the pile at Labenne are shown in Figure 6. The sensors were located at a distance, h normalised by pile diameter, D . The local shear stress, τ_f , measured at any location on the pile shaft were seen to closely mirror the CPT cone resistance, q_c , profile.

Figure 6 Shear stress measured during the installation in loose to medium dense sand (after Lehane 1993).

The local shear stress, τ_f mobilised during a load test to failure was seen to follow a Mohr – Coulomb failure criterion and was dependent on the equalised radial effective stress, σ'_{rc} ; a component related to the increase in radial stress as a result of dilation, $\Delta\sigma'_{rd}$; and the interface friction angle at failure, δ_f . The ratio (f_t/f_c) is 1.0 for compression loading and 0.75 for tension loading.

$$\tau_f = \frac{f_t}{f_c} (\sigma'_{rc} + \Delta\sigma'_{rd}) \cdot \tan\delta_f \quad [1]$$

At a given sensor location, the ratio τ_f / q_c was similar at both the Labenne and Dunkirk sites, despite large difference in the CPT q_c profiles. Values were highest near the pile toe and reduced as the distance from the pile tip, h , increased. This phenomenon known as friction fatigue is incorporated in the unified design approach by reducing the predicted equalised radial effective stress as h/D increases.

Gavin and Lehane (2003) and Igoe et al. (2011) report a direct correlation between τ_f/q_c or σ'_{rc}/q_c mobilised by an open-ended pile and the degree of plugging experienced during pile installation. White et al. (2005) used a cavity expansion analogy to suggest that σ'_{rc} acting on an open-ended pile varies with the effective area ratio, A_{re} , raised to a power of 0.3 to 0.45, where PLR is the plug length ratio (=soil plug length/pile penetration) and the D_i is the inner diameter of the pile:

$$A_{re} = 1 - PLR \left(\frac{D_i}{D} \right)^2 \quad [2]$$

Based on statistical interpretation of the unified database Lehane et al. (2020) propose the equalised radial effective stress, σ'_{rc} from equation 1 be estimated using:

$$\sigma'_{rc} = \left(\frac{q_c}{44} \right) A_{re}^{0.3} \left[\text{Max} \left(\frac{h}{D} \right) \right]^{-0.4} \quad [3]$$

Considering Equation 1, $\Delta\sigma'_{rd}$ is the increase in radial effective stress caused by dilation at the pile-soil interface. Lehane and Jardine (1994) showed that $\Delta\sigma'_{rd}$ values could be predicted using cavity expansion theory, and were inversely proportional to the pile diameter. This suggests that the effects of dilation are not significant for large diameter offshore piles but could dominate the behaviour of small scale model piles. Lehane et al (2020) suggest the following equation to estimate interface dilation, where σ'_v is the vertical effective stress and d_{CPT} is the diameter of a standard CPT probe (35.7mm):

$$\Delta\sigma'_{rd} = \left(\frac{q_c}{10} \right) \left(\frac{q_c}{\sigma'_v} \right)^{-0.33} \left(\frac{d_{CPT}}{D} \right) \quad [4]$$

Interpretation of interface shear tests by Liu et al. (2019) has shown that δ_f in Equation 1 is relatively insensitive to particle size, mineralogy and stress level and in the absence of site-specific interface shear tests they suggest a constant $\delta_f = 29^\circ$ be adopted for the unified database piles.

3.3 Base Resistance

Gavin and Lehane (2003) and others show that the base resistance developed during static loading of an open-ended pile is controlled by the CPT q_c value at the pile toe and the degree of plugging experienced during the final stages of pile installation. The degree of plugging is expressed as the final filling ratio, $FFR = \text{incremental increase in soil plug}$

length/increase in pile penetration. For large diameter open-ended piles, A_{re} is given by:

$$A_{re} = 1 - FFR \left(\frac{D_i}{D} \right)^2 \approx 1 - PLR \left(\frac{D_i}{D} \right)^2 \quad [5]$$

Lehane et al. (2020) compiled a database of 18 load tests on instrumented open-ended piles. The base resistance mobilised at a pile base displacement of 10% of the pile diameter, $q_{b0.1}$, normalised by the CPT value averaged at the pile base, q_p , See Figure 7 could be described as:

$$\frac{q_{b0.1}}{q_p} = 0.12 + 0.38 A_{re} \quad [6]$$

Figure 7 Variation of normalised end bearing resistance with degree of plugging during installation (after Lehane et al. 2020)

4 EXTENSION OF DESIGN METHODS

4.1 Background

Despite the advances described in the preceding sections, significant work is ongoing to determine the influence of a number of factors such as time effects, cyclic loading, geometry and installation effects on the behaviour of pile foundations for the offshore renewables industry.

4.2 Time Effects

Positive gains in capacity with time (i.e. set-up) of driven piles in clay as a result of dissipation of excess pore pressures induced by driving is a well-understood phenomenon. Set-up also known as ageing of driven piles in sand is a less well understood phenomenon. Many studies have measured ageing, Jardine et al. (2006), Lim and Lehane (2014), Karlsrud et. al. (2013) amongst others. A trend for an increase in shaft resistance from a minima immediately after installation to a value double the post-installation resistance approximately 100 days after installation is regularly observed.

Gavin et al. (2013) report axial tension load tests performed on 340 mm diameter, open-ended steel tubular piles driven into dense sand in Blessington. The load-displacement test data shown in Figure 8 reveal a general trend for increase in ultimate shaft capacity as the time between installation and first load-test increases. Nevertheless, anomalies consisting of

piles with unexpectedly low resistance, such as the pile tested on Day 30 in Figure 8 are not uncommon. Several studies have suggested that the end of installation pile resistance is sensitive to factors such as hard-driving, Lim and Lehane (2014), Anusic et al. (2019). Research is ongoing to understand the role of installation method, pile geometry and geological conditions amongst other factors on time effects.

Figure 8 Influence of ageing period on the tension resistance of open-ended piles in dense sand (after Gavin et al. 2013)

4.3 Cyclic Loading

In the previous section the potential benefits of allowing piles to age in-situ was considered. In the offshore environment, pile foundations are continuously subjected to axial cyclic loading from wind and wave action. While cyclic design guidelines for shallow foundations are reasonably well established accurately predicting the axial cyclic loading response of driven piles is particularly challenging due to the complex soil stress history at the pile-soil interface.

The axial cyclic response of piles in sand has been shown by to be affected by the number of load cycles, (N); the mean shaft load (Q_{mean}) and cyclic amplitude (Q_{cyc}) as shown in Fig.9.

Figure 9 Definition of cyclic loading parameters for axially loaded (after Igoe and Gavin, 2021)

While a number of model laboratory scale cyclic pile studies have been conducted, there is a dearth of field cyclic tests on driven piles in sand. A single case history in silica sand exists from the Imperial College London, ICL test programme at Loon Plage, Dunkirk, France. The field tests investigated the combined effects of ageing and cyclic loading on the capacity of driven piles in sands, as part of the GOPAL pile test campaign, Jardine et al. (2006) and Jardine and Standing (2012). The tests involved a number of static and cyclic load tests on seven, 457mm diameter steel piles driven into the dense marine sand deposit at Dunkirk.

Igoe and Gavin (2021) report a complimentary series of axial static and cyclic load tests performed at a range of ages on four, 340mm diameter, steel open-ended piles at the Blessington test site. The test results were interpreted to consider various behaviour states:

- (i) Stable cycling, where the pile head displacements accumulate slowly over hundreds of cycles.
- (ii) Unstable cycling, where head displacements develop rapidly leading to failure within 100 cycles.
- (iii) Metastable load cycling, where head displacements accumulated at a moderate rate leading to failure between 100 – 1000 cycles.

Cyclic interaction diagrams were proposed to express how cyclic loading parameters Number of cycles, N , Q_{mean} and Q_{cyc} affect the piles cyclic response relative to the max static shaft capacity available in tension prior to cycling, See Figure 10.

Figure 10 Cyclic load interaction diagram for pile in sand (Igoe and Gavin 2021)

Given the relatively strict displacement and rotation criteria for laterally loaded piles, developing models to predict plastic strains caused by cyclic loading are an area of intensive research interest. The problem is illustrated with data from a centrifuge study by Li et al. (2022) of the impact of loading level, defined here as $\zeta_b (= H/H_{ult})$ on the lateral loading response of a monopile in dense sand, See Figure 11. A number of studies have suggested that simple models of the form proposed by Klinkvort and Hededal (2013) could provide excellent predictions of the pile response. Notwithstanding this fundamental advances in our understanding are necessary and are being pursued in a number of major national and international research programmes (See Kementzetidis et al. 2022, Liu and Kaynia (2022), Liu et al. (2022) and others.

Figure 11 Pile lateral one-way cyclic loading response (Li et al. 2022).

4.4 Geometry Effects

As monopile diameters increase and L/D ratios reduce, these structures, are less like piles and are often referred to as intermediate foundations. A number of workers have studied the combined loading problem for shallow and skirted foundations identifying interaction effects such that the horizontal lateral load, H , and moment, M , capacity of the footing depend on the current vertical load level, V e.g. Butterfield and Gottardi, (1994), Nova and Montrasio, (1991), Bransby and Randolph (1998). Li et al. (2022) investigated this load-interaction effects on monopiles in the geotechnical centrifuge at TU Delft.

Figure 12 Effect of V/V_u on the lateral loading response of monopiles, (a) $L/D = 5$, (b) $L/D = 3$)

Piles with L/D of 3 and 5 were considered in the analysis. The impact of increasing the ratio of the vertical applied load, V to the ultimate vertical resistance, V_u (defined as the final jacking resistance of the pile) is shown in Figure 12. In Figure 12a, the data for the pile with $L/D = 5$ shows that increasing the vertical force increases both the lateral capacity of the stiffness of the piles. In contrast, the data for the pile with $L/D = 3$ shown in Figure 12b indicates that a transition point is reached in the ratio of V/V_u , above which the load is detrimental to the lateral response of the pile.

The results can be summarized in an interaction diagram See Figure 13 where the horizontal load capacity with zero vertical load, $H_{u,0}$ is compared with the enhanced capacity, $H_{u,v}$. The data show that the addition of a vertical load was always beneficial. For piles with $L/D = 3$ the lateral bearing capacity increased initially as the vertical load increased. The normalized pile lateral capacity reached a peak value when the vertical load was between $0.4V_u$ and $0.5V_u$. For higher loads the beneficial effect of vertical loading reduced. A parabolic failure locus similar in shape to those reported for shallow foundations by Nova and Montrasio (1991) appears to match the pile response well.

For piles with L/D of 5, the pile horizontal lateral capacity increased non-linearly with increasing vertical load, the benefit increasing as vertical load level increased.

Figure 13 Influence of vertical loading on the lateral bearing capacity of the model piles

5 CONCLUSIONS

Major advances in our understanding of the physical mechanisms controlling pile behaviour have allowed step-changes in the reliability of pile design methods. These have largely been achieved by collaborative projects between academia and industry. However, significant challenges remain. Some of these include:

- (i) Installation methods – a number of novel installation methods are being developed to reduce the environmental impact of driving large diameter monopiles.
- (ii) Offshore projects are being performed in geological conditions that we have limited experience of, for

example hard rock, glauconitic sand and regions prone to tsunamis and earthquakes.

- (iii) Floating wind will provide a whole new set of challenges in geotechnical engineer, including the sensitivity of anchor systems to fatigue.

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Geothermal Energy (GE); Unrealised Remedy for Climate Action?

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ABSTRACT: This paper examines the current development of Geothermal Energy (GE) in a global and national context. It concludes that realising the potential of the sector requires significant changes to energy policy, regulatory arrangements and risk assessment and indicates that these changes are underway.

KEY WORDS: Geoscience; Geothermal Energy, Renewable Energy, Climate Action

1 INTRODUCTION

Geothermal Energy (GE) is the harnessing of a theoretically endless source of energy from the earth and contributes to the decarbonising of energy production. Radioactive decay generates continuous searing heat of more than 5000°C in the Earth's core. Radiating outwards, the heat warms rocks, water and gas in the geomaterial that makes up our planet. The resulting geysers and hot springs are sources of geothermal energy, but most heat collects as pockets of dry heat that must be accessed by drilling and released as steam by injection of water.

Reflecting the high temperatures found in the earth's core, earth temperatures increase with depth, usually at a rate of 25°C per km. This is known as the geothermal gradient. GE utilises the geothermal gradient to harvest hot water, either by extraction or by injection and recovery.

GE is generally considered under two headings-; power generation and district heating. Power generation is provided by waters with temperatures of c +130°C, while district heating is provided by waters at lesser temperatures of 50-100°C.

At present, GE is largely confined to areas where the geothermal gradient is high i.e., where the cover rocks are thinner above the hottest areas of the subsurface. Areas of lower geothermal gradients can also be developed; they require access by deeper drilling.

The European Union (EU) recognises the potential of GE by supporting research and analysis of commercial aspects of the sector. Geoscience Ireland (GI) is part of an EU funded project to examine opportunities for European Small and

Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in the sector. In Ireland, new geothermal policies are under preparation, supported by enthusiastic research, professional and vocational groups.

Significant challenges face the development of the GE sector, including geological risk, regulatory arrangements and operational issues. A number of EU demonstration projects are addressing these risks.

2 GE GLOBAL PERSPECTIVES

As noted, the temperature increases with depth. In some places with tectonic plate movements or active volcanoes, like California or Iceland, the heat is closer to the surface enabling easier access to the resource (Fig.1).

There, geothermal heat and power stations are routine and are cost competitive with gas or wind power. Wells drilled into the rock intersect with hydrothermal reservoirs, and the superheated water brought to the surface runs turbines to create electricity, and is used for heating or industry.

Recent improvements and falling costs in drilling technology, and lower temperature electricity generation, mean that the potential for geothermal heat and power is spreading to areas where the temperatures are not so extreme and the geological activity lies far in the past, but has left a legacy of hot rocks. In such areas, Engineered Geothermal Systems can be used.

(Information from the British Geological Survey and the Icelandic National Energy Authority)

Figure 1: GE Power Plants

Table 1: GE Challenges

Technological challenges	Environmental concerns
Reliable predictive resource assessment	Seismicity, Subsidence
Cost-effective drilling and completion technology for HT (>300°C) and deep wells (>5 km) wells	Air and Water quality
Improvement of power systems efficiency @ zero emission	Licensing, Environmental Impact Assessment and Social issues
Materials and equipment life time extension in harsh environment (pressure, scaling and corrosion)	Territorial integration
High temperature (>50°C) thermal energy storage	Information sharing and public engagement.
Mineral extraction from geothermal sources	

Figure 2: Geo-energy Europe participants

Geothermal electricity is generated commercially in 25 countries, including the USA, Indonesia, Germany, Kenya and Iceland. A further 82 countries use geothermal heat directly – for heating buildings, agriculture, horticulture, fish farming, industry and leisure facilities.

Global geothermal power generation capacity stood at 15,608 MW at the year-end 2020. The current pandemic situation clearly slowed down development, but new capacity is expected in coming years. It is estimated that 8% of global electricity supplies serving 17% of the world’s population could be provided by GE. However, the International Energy Agency suggests that this technology is not on track with the Net Zero Emissions by 2050 Scenario, which requires 13% annual increases in generation over 2021-2030, corresponding to average annual capacity expansions of ~3.6 GW i.e., 13%

per annum. Policies to help reduce costs and mitigate predevelopment risks are needed to increase geothermal-based power generation.

The oil and gas industry experience in complex drilling operations provides a useful pivot for drilling contractors undertaking geothermal; a good example is found in the Eavor project in Alberta which involved deep drilling with multiple offsets.

3 GE IN EUROPE

The EU supports GE research and development through two important programmes.

1. The GEO-ENERGY EUROPE metacluster brings together the European know-how, technologies and experience in geo-energy, with an emphasis on its SMEs’

offer and a focus on deep geothermal energy. GEO-ENERGY EUROPE currently represents over 600 members, including 300+ SMEs, from 23 EU countries, and covers the entire deep geothermal value chain.

2. The GEO-ENERGY EUROPE 2 project is funded by the European Union's COSME Programme Grant Agreement number: 951195 (2020-2022). COSME is a European programme for the Competitiveness of Small and Medium sized Enterprises. The objective is of the COSME programme is to help European businesses to reach their full potential by an access to finance, markets, and by improving business conditions and encouraging entrepreneurship. A key element of this objective is an evaluation of opportunities in four key markets – Chile, Canada, Kenya and Costa Rica- by way of Market Study Visits. Covid 19 restrictions greatly hampered this activity which was due to take place from 2020; hence these Visits have been confined to 2022. Consequently, the delivery of Cooperation and Business Agreements which were planned outcomes has been limited. However, the interaction of the partners with one another and with the target countries has led to capacity building, cross sectoral innovation and communication delivered mainly on virtual platforms.

Geoscience Ireland, along with Geological Survey Ireland (GSI), leads the Market Study Visit elements of the GEO-ENERGY EUROPE 2 project. The participants are shown in Figure 2.

Another EU project- the European Technology and Innovation Platform on Deep Geothermal (ETIP-DT) identifies technical and policy challenges for the sector as shown in Table 1:

4 EU ENERGY POLICY AND GE

In addition to the support programmes outlined above, the EU requires member states to deliver integrated national energy and climate plans. EU policy points to delivery of 40% of energy from renewable sources by 2030. The European Green Deal recognises the role of GE in reaching this target. Energy security issues, now sharply in focus following Russian aggression in Ukraine, also points to further EU support for GE which is local, constantly available and a sustainable replacement for fossil fuels.

5 GE IN IRELAND

Ireland's GE potential has been promoted by the Geothermal Association of Ireland (GAI) and Geological Survey Ireland (GSI) for many years. The absence of a regulatory framework has hindered GE development. In contrast to the EU average of 23%, Ireland relies on only 6.3% of renewables for its final energy consumption for heating and cooling while Sweden leads at 66%.

Climate Action initiatives have refocused attention on the sector and has seen the inclusion of GE for District Heating in the Climate Action Plan 2021. A number of policy documents have been published in recent years including a GSI Assessment of Geothermal Energy for District Heating in Ireland; a 2020 Non-Technical Roadmap for a Policy and Regulatory Framework and a Draft Action Plan and Draft Policy Statement in 2021. Legislation is planned under a

Geoscience Bill by the end of 2023 to deal inter alia with legal, planning and regulatory issues for the sector.

Geological Survey Ireland has dedicated GE staff and provides technical support to government on technical and regulatory issues. GSI is developing a National Geothermal Database- an important element in de-risking projects. It also engages in public information and engagement. The Irish Centre for Research in Applied Geoscience (iCRAG) also conducts research in the area and supports GSI's public engagement activities.

Figure 3: Geological features influencing GE in the Dublin region

The nascent GE sector already has some interesting recent and current projects in Ireland. These include a shallow geothermal well network for IKEA in Dublin; an exploratory 1 km deep borehole by GSI in TU Dublin which showed a downhole temperature of 38C; geothermal wells at Trinity College Dublin and University College Dublin and a proposal for space heating at Offaly County Council. Geological elements effecting future drilling are shown on Figure 3.

The Geological Survey of Northern Ireland (GSNI) has led a series of seminars on GE and has contributed to increased awareness and to recent energy policy developments. Northern Ireland enjoys a higher geothermal gradient than elsewhere on the island and has significant potential for development. In Britain, GE is recognised in policy as a contributor to climate action and a number of projects in Cornwall are being developed to generate power, provide district heating and to win critical metals from hot brines.

Some Irish companies active in the sector are Priority Drilling which recently completed a 2km deep borehole in Cornwall; Meehan Drilling, also active in Cornwall and GDGEO which has published policy research.

6 CONCLUSIONS

GAI and GSI among others have long recognised that the Geothermal sector has considerable potential, as yet largely unrealised in Ireland. Climate Action policies have reactivated attention to policy and technical issues which have seen legislative and technical initiatives. There are capable scientists, engineers and contractors in Ireland who can contribute to meeting the pent- up demand in realising geothermal potential. Geotechnical engineers and geologists have a significant role to play in investigating the subsurface, minimising seismic, subsidence and environmental risks and the Geotechnical Society of Ireland can also play its part in examining and solving these issues.

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Offshore and Onshore Wind

An Overview and Benefits of Ground Improvement for Gravity Based Wind Turbine Foundations for Design & Construction

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ABSTRACT: In 2021 the Irish Government set out its plan to halve all emissions by the year 2030 and set a target of net zero by 2050. Renewable energy will have a key role to play in meeting these targets by providing low emission energy to the Irish market. The construction industry will also see an increase in demand for more sustainable construction solutions, due to the necessity to reduce the carbon footprint on projects, combined with rising material and energy costs. From a geotechnical standpoint, the application of ground improvement in the context of onshore gravity-based wind turbine foundations, is now common practice across the globe as a viable alternative to traditional deep foundation solutions. The flexibility of ground improvement design in variable soil conditions, the speed of execution and the capacity to adapt to locally available resources allows for a potential low carbon, high speed and cost-effective solution. Over the past three decades, there have been significant advances in geotechnical and ground improvement design together with substantial developments and simplification of ground improvement execution methods. This progress has opened the door for the application of these techniques to onshore wind farm projects. Ground conditions in Ireland are well suited to ground improvement techniques due predominantly to the type of ground encountered and the general depths of ground improvement required in superficial soils. Ground improvement technologies are advancing and developing year on year and these techniques can make a significant contribution to the development of both the Irish geotechnical and the renewable energy markets.

KEY WORDS: Ground Improvement; Renewable Energy; Onshore Wind Farm Foundation Design ; Controlled Modulus Column – Rigid Inclusion

1 INTRODUCTION

The Irish Government has set out its climate action plan which details that 80% of electricity should be generated through means of renewable energy by 2030 and put forward the ambitious target of net zero by 2050.

Renewable energies will perform a key role in delivering this ambitious plan. The development of both on and offshore shore wind energy and other sources such as solar, hydro along community based projects contributing up to 500MW of renewable energy, will be driven by multi-billion euro investment over the next decade.

The construction industry has a large part to play so that these targets may be achieved through more efficient and optimised methods of design and working. According to the IGBC approximately 11% of all national emissions are attributed to producing and transporting construction materials for buildings and infrastructure projects alone.

There is a clear demand within the industry for more sustainable and less energy intensive methods of construction.

In the context of the geotechnical challenges to infrastructure projects, ground improvement can play a leading role. The simplified concept of ground improvement details for any given structure, to use what capacity is present in the soil and complement this in the most optimised manner possible. Sometimes this can be without addition of material through densification or with the addition of locally sourced materials, including, but not limited to, material sourced within the site if feasible. The knock-on benefits for this are numerous including, but not limited to, a reduction in quantities of imported materials and consequently a significant reduction in the need to remove materials offsite.

Ground improvement techniques are generally simple, they reduce complicated interaction between various parties working within a project and generally have a secondary effect of reducing the project impact on its surrounding environment. This article will review the design and implementation of ground improvement at on shore wind farms projects and highlight some of the benefits.

2 WIND TURBINE FOUNDATION DESIGN

Foundations for wind turbines are typically octagonal or circular in nature with diameters varying from 15m to 30m approximately.

Figure 28. Typical Gravity Foundation

To extract and determine the loading conditions for a wind turbine foundation, various conceptual scenarios considering the various stages of the turbine design life including assembly, power generation, extreme winds, safety mode, breakdown and disassembly are analysed. Hundreds of different conceptual load cases are reviewed to determine the governing load case envelope.

Figure 29 – Loading forces and bending analysis

Results are then classed in three categories: 1. Quasi-permanent, 2. Rare and 3. Accidental. For each load case, the value of vertical and horizontal resultant forces are provided along with torsion and overturning with buoyancy also being considered where applicable.

Each load case is factored to define loads at Serviceability Load State (SLS) and Ultimate Limit State (ULS).

Load case	Limit states	Partial weighting factors for stresses			
		F_z	H	M	Water
DLC _{Qp}	ULS _{Fund}	1.0 or 1.35	1.8	1.8	1.125 x 1.05
	SLS _{perm}	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
DLC _{Rare}	ULS _{Fund}	1.0 or 1.35	1.5	1.5	1.125 x 1.05
	SLS _{Rare}	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
DLC _{Acc}	ULS _{Acc}	0.9 or 1.1	1.1	1.1	1.0

Figure 30 – Typical weighting factors for load case

Once stresses below the foundation pad have been established, as with any classical foundation design, the compressed zone at the underside of the gravity base can be determined using the relevant weighting factor for each individual load case as shown below in figure 4.

Figure 31 - Relative compressed areas for contact pressures under foundations (Racinais et al, 2016).

3 TECHNICAL REQUIREMENTS REQUIRED FOR GROUND IMPROVEMENT

Once the stress analysis is complete, the weighted loading is translated into relevant specifications:

- Maximum and total differential settlements (typically 3mm/m)
- Minimum stiffness
 - o Dynamic stiffness $K_{\phi \text{ DYN}}$
 - o Deformation related stiffness.
- Check for sliding resistance and overturning
- Bearing capacity considering serviceability limit state
- Bearing capacity considering ultimate limit state
- Bearing capacity considering accidental load case

4 GROUND CONDITIONS FOR WIND FARM PROJECTS

Due to the nature and functionality of turbines, onshore wind farm projects tend to be located in remote areas where topography and soil conditions may be of a varying but very often poor nature. In Ireland, deep and soft geotechnical conditions are often encountered, varying from organic deposits and peat, to layers of glacial till to karstic limestone under loose granular material containing cobbles and boulders mixed with lenses of finer soils. Ground improvement can serve as a potential solution to these problems.

5 GROUND IMPROVEMENT TECHNIQUE & DESIGN

5.1 Selection of ground improvement

The ground improvement design is decided upon considering a number of factors:

- Nature of the load and structure to be supported
- Nature of soil and soil profile characteristics (depth of soft soil, position of water table, etc.)
- Specification requirement of the foundation
- The availability of material surrounding the site – concrete, cement, stone, sand etc

Figure 32 – Selection of ground improvement technique according to soil type

In order for any ground improvement technique to be fully effective, it must be suited to the problem that is being solved. Any one ground improvement technique is not suitable and applicable to all ground conditions, Hamidi and Varaksin (2012).

5.2 Examples of ground improvement projects in varying soil conditions

As previously discussed, by introducing a ground improvement technique, the idea is to provide the necessary specification for adequate performance of the foundation or structure by limiting the volume of material removed from site and reduce even more significantly, where possible, the volume of material imported into the site. The aim is to work with the soil on the site in question. Reducing the required volume of exported and imported material reduces risks on a project planning. This can potentially provide savings to the overall project cost.

A large variety of ground improvement techniques have been used in the past to improve soil characteristics under turbine foundations.

In the context of wind farm projects, the techniques vary from both ends of the spectrum. At one end there are inclusion techniques where locally sourced materials are added to soft or fine loose soils to obtain the necessary criteria as required. At the other end, there is densification techniques where in-situ soils are compacted directly with no additional material needed. In some cases, it may be a combination of both additional material and densification.

Consolidation techniques are generally not considered for wind turbine foundations due to the high bearing stresses experienced at the base of the foundation. The different range of techniques are presented above in figure 5.

Some simple examples include the following projects:

Project: Ilza Wind Farm II, Poland
Soil conditions: soft sandy silt
Technique: Soil Mixing

At the Ilza Wind Farm, a combination of cement water grout is mixed with in-situ soils to form a stiff and composite foundation system to support the turbine. This type of solution complemented the in-situ soil conditions well and allowed for reduction of stone importation thanks to the grout mix.

Figure 33 – Soil Mixing - Ilza Wind Farm project II

Project: Nouakchott Wind Farm, Mauritania
 Soil Conditions: loose to medium dense silty sands with layers of clay.
 Technique: Vibro Compaction and Vibro Stone Columns executed using VREX bottom feed method.

Figure 34 – Vibro Stone Column Works - Nouakchott Wind Farm project

What was originally identified as a vibro stone column solution, this project detailed a combination of vibro compaction and vibro stone columns.

Upon inspection of conditions on site with some additional soil investigation, it was observed that there were various layers within the soil profile that were deemed compactible or compactible with reduced quantity of stone material. This was due to the interpreted low fine contents within certain layers and the relatively well graded nature of the soil as shown in figure 8, section B.

As with the previous example in Poland, this project allowed for a saving of stone material over the project in what was a very isolated site location where stone was difficult to source.

Figure 35 – Analysis of granulometry for Nouakchott Wind Farm Project

Project: Cape Bridge Wind Farm, Australia
 Soil Conditions: loose fine sands
 Technique: Dynamic compaction

Figure 36 – Dynamic Compaction - Cape Bridge wind farm project

The use of dynamic compaction (DC) is one of the most efficient and economical techniques available for the implementation of foundation systems. Developed by Louis Menard in France in the 1960's, the technique is now used widely across the globe on a number of different project types from ports to warehousing to energy.

The application of DC on this project in Cape Bridge, Australia removed the need for importation of any material for the ground improvement. The densification of in-situ material is immediate following compaction meaning foundation construction could commence instantly as soon as the ground improvement works were complete.

6 CASE STUDY - MALLECO WIND FARM PROJECT, CHILE

6.1 Description of Project

The Malleco wind farm project is located in the Araucania region of Chile near the town of Collipulli. The development detailed the construction of 77# nr turbines varying from 3.45 – 3.6MW for a combined capacity of 273MW. The turbine height varied from 120-140m.

The site stretches over an approximate radius of 10km with a terrain that can be described as undulating in nature as is typical of wind farm projects. Of the 77# nr turbines on the wind farm, 74# nr turbine locations were found to have poor soil conditions and would require intervention in order to ensure the achievement of specifications including bearing capacity, settlement control and minimum stiffness.

6.2 Soil Conditions

A generic profile for the project could be described as follows:

- Soft to firm sandy clay and silt with some gravel
- Stiff, very stiff to hard silty clay with sand and gravel
- Cemented volcanic gravels / Weathered mudstone and siltstone

Despite the project being spread over a large area, the soil profile was found to be quite consistent however the thicknesses of the problematic soft to firm sandy clay & silt identified at the surface tended to vary.

Typically, this layer displayed relatively high content of fines with a medium to low plasticity. The range of values for this layer are presented below:

- Liquid Limit – 40% - 78%
- Plastic Index – 5% - 30%

Fines content varied greatly across the site with values in the range of 4% up to 90%. This can be explained by the intermittent layers of granular material within the profile.

Considering all soil investigation information, to optimise the treatment process six different soil profiles consisting of similar depths of compressible material were compiled across the site. These are presented below in figure 10.

Figure 37 – Soil Profiles – Malleco Wind Farm Project

6.3 Specifications required

The specification required for the wind turbine foundation were as follows:

- SLS and ULS bearing capacities check for each separate load case
- Differential settlement $\Delta h_{diff} < 3 \text{ mm/m}$
- Dynamic rotational stiffness of the foundation $K_{\phi, dyn} > 57 \text{ GN.m/rad}$
- Dynamic horizontal stiffness of the foundation $K_{h, dyn} > 12 \text{ MN.m/rad}$

Type of DLC	Limit state	N [kN]	H [kN]	M [kN.m]
DLC QP Prob.:1e-2	SLS QP	5 672	641	90 301
DLC Rare 32PREogVim11(fam151)	SLS Rare	5 628	896	129 400
DLC Rare 32PREogVim11(fam151)	ULS Fund	5 628	896	129 400
DLC Rare 32PREogVim11(fam151)	ULS Fund	5 628	896	129 400
DLC Acc 23CoEogVrp8(fam133)	ULS Acc	5 597	1 041	141 400
DLC Acc Resulting Tower Bottom Seismic load - 4 ETG 1.015	ULS Seis	3 577	1 166	118 336
DLC Acc Resulting Tower Bottom Seismic load - 3 ETG 1.015	ULS Seis	8 538	1 166	118 336

Figure 38 – Design load cases at the base of the foundation

6.4 Ground Improvement Solution

The ground conditions were insufficient in terms of bearing capacity, differential settlement and rotational and dynamic stiffness. Liquefaction was also reviewed and determined to be not a problem on this site.

The two solutions initially considered for the site in order to address the geotechnical hazards were deep foundation piling and Controlled Modulus Columns (CMC) – rigid inclusions.

The CMC is a technique first developed by Menard in France in the 1990s and like all soil reinforcement techniques, the principle of ‘controlled modulus column’ is not necessarily to stop settlement but to control it to within acceptable limits, Coghlan et al. (2016). The CMC system works with a load transfer mattress (LTM) to limit the transmission of horizontal stress to the columns however a key role of the LTM is to optimise the distribution of stresses between the columns and the soft soil layer.

On the Malleco Wind Farm project, the CMC option was retained due to several reasons:

- The technique was the more economical solution because:
 - o The nature of the technique in comparison to the piling solution resulted in a substantial reduction in concrete required for the foundation system.
 - o As liquefaction was ruled out as a geotechnical hazard, the CMC columns did not require reinforcement therefore removing the need to import steel into the project for the ground improvement scope.
- On what were tight milestones, the risk on the foundation scope planning was significantly reduced

due to the reduction in concrete demand, along with the removal of the need for steel on the project meaning less reliance on material importation. This is key to meet the delivery date of turbines themselves and towers later on in the project.

- Speed of execution also provided significant benefits for the project planning. A combination of the manoeuvrability of the CMC rig and the sequence of works proposed on the project by the subcontractor allowed for the completion of a minimum of one full turbine on average per day with peaks of three turbines complete per day during the works.
- Easier interaction between the specialist subcontractor and the contractor on site. There is no steel connection with the foundation base to contend with, therefore, the contractor can take over the site as soon as the curing period of 7 days has elapsed and start the foundation construction works. This is complemented by the fact that there is little or no spoil during the CMC process which is conducive to a quick handover.
- The design of the gravity foundation base can be optimised due primarily to the fact that there is one uniform stiffness below the foundation base as opposed to numerous point loads. It also allows for a more straightforward design process.

Figure 39 – Platform during CMC works – Malleco Wind Farm Project

6.5 CMC - Proposed sequence of works

The sequence of works for execution was as follows:

Step 1 – excavation of foundation footprint and installation of platform

Step 2 – Execution of CMC technique

Step 3 – Construction of foundation base

Step 4 – Installation of overburden

6.6 Controlled Modulus Column (CMC) Design

CMC diameters typically vary from 200mm to 420mm. Full displacement with diameter of 320mm was selected for this project. CMC can, in some cases, be executed using flighted auger however displacement mode was chosen on this project. The main reasons for this were as follows:

- soil conditions allowed for it but also because displacement mode has little or no spoil
- layers displaying low fines can be densified and improved during the execution process.

These were strong contributing factors in the choice of execution method with the latter being strongly beneficial to the design of this ground improvement system.

Figure 40 – Execution of CMC ground improvement on Malleco wind farm project

Based on the various load cases as shown in figure 11, an analysis was performed on the foundation behaviour. The stress distribution below the foundation was established and a CMC layout was then compiled.

Figure 41 – CMC Layout per profile – Malleco Wind Farm

CMC is by nature robust and adaptable to variations in the soil conditions. Of the 74# nr turbines executed, as previously mentioned, six soil profiles were defined as shown in Figure 10. This exercise was performed to allow an optimised design of CMC layout and to simplify both design and execution phases.

The characteristics of a load transfer mattress are also defined at this stage considering a well compacted granular material with a high modulus and angle of friction. On this project, the material used was a granular material with a granulometry of 2-6cm and a thickness of 60cm. It was placed in two steps.

The LTM had the added benefit that it can double up as a platform for the CMC rig and is required to comply with the following control using a plate load testing prior to works commencing:

- $E_{v2} > 50\text{Mpa}$
- $E_{v2}/E_{v1} < 2$

Figure 42 – Foundation stress distribution (L) with load per CMC analysis (R)

The various calculation checks are then performed using the Menard in house software which is based the analytical model MV as per ASIRI (IREX, 2012) as shown in figure 15.

Step 1 - Equivalent deformation modulus – A first calculation is performed considering the grid, typical loading and soil column interaction in order to establish the Equivalent Young's Modulus $E_{Y,eq,LT}$ of the equivalent layer.

Step 2 – The checks for minimum stiffness values are subsequently performed using the $E_{Y,eq,LT}$ calculated in step 1:

- static long-term vertical stiffness $K_{V,LT}$
- the static long-term rotational stiffness $K_{\phi,LT}$
- The static long-term horizontal stiffness $K_{h,LT}$
- Rotational stiffness $K_{\phi,dyn}$ and horizontal stiffness $K_{h,dyn}$

Step 3 – Deformation calculation – checks are performed to ensure that deformations are within allowable limits:

- Maximum and minimum settlements
- Average settlement at the centre of the foundation
- Rotation
- Differential settlement considering maximum and minimum settlements.

Step 4 – Bearing capacity

For bearing, a first check is performed on “global” resistance and stability of the foundation considering the DLC ULS case load or in this case due to the location of the site, the DLC ULC Acc considering the seismic load case.

A “local” resistance check is also performed considering the most highly loaded CMC.

Figure 43 – Example of stress distribution in CMC / soil interface

Step 5 - Final checks are then performed to ensure the integrity of the column and a check for compressive stress does not exceed the allowable compressive strength of the mortar or concrete, f_{cd} .

The verification of the inclusion integrity in terms of axial force and bending moment in the column is carried out in accordance with the half-moon method derived from the Eurocode 2, section 12:

$$N_{Ed} \leq N_{Rd} = A_{ref} \cdot f_{cd} \quad (1)$$

Where;

- N_{Ed} is the design value of the applied axial force
- f_{cd} is the design compressive strength of the CMC grout
- A_{ref} is the compressive area of the CMC section under vertical load and bending moment

Figure 44 – Verification of CMC section integrity

7 CONCLUSION

In the context of achieving the goals set out by the Irish government in the climate action plan 2021, ground improvement is well placed to contribute within the construction industry.

The ground improvement process allows a high flexibility to deal with geotechnical problems on infrastructural projects

including wind farms as shown above, in a way that allows the required foundation specifications to be respected but also decreasing volume of material used during the construction process, faster execution times and ultimately lower cost. The technologies are simple to implement and contribute to a significant reduction in risk with regards to project planning due to reduction in the volume of material required and simplified interface between the various parties on site.

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Comparison of geotechnical design criteria for offshore monopiles

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ABSTRACT: The offshore wind industry has evolved over the past decade with significant technological advances driven by the need for offshore wind energy to approach subsidy free status in favourable locations. The relatively low margin in offshore wind necessitates lean and efficient designs and nowhere is this more prevalent than in the turbine foundations. This paper discusses and compares the various geotechnical design criteria which govern the monopile dimensions.

KEY WORDS: Monopiles; Geotechnical; Offshore Wind; Critical Length.

1 INTRODUCTION

Driven by growing concerns about climate change and the need to decarbonise our energy production, the global offshore wind market has exhibited a rapid expansion over the past decade with an average 30% increase per year since 2010 (International Energy Agency, 2019). During this period, a number of significant technological advances have reduced the levelized cost of offshore wind energy. The foundations supporting offshore wind turbine structures, offer significant scope for optimisation due to the high degree of uncertainty in the engineering design process. This is partly driven by the variability and complex behaviour of soils. Moreover, foundations typically represent between 25-34% of the cost (Bhattacharya 2019). The high costs of the foundations are a result of not only the high volumes of steel required but also the costs of transportation and installation which require the hire of specialist equipment and vessels. Monopile foundations, which are large diameter (ranging from 4m to 12m) steel tubes driven into the ground, represent around 80% of all offshore wind turbine foundations installed to date and are likely to continue to be the most common foundation solution for offshore wind for the next decade (Smith, 2018). As a result, there has been a substantial research effort recently aimed at optimising the design of monopiles supporting offshore wind turbines.

Geotechnical Engineers typically model the monopile-soil interaction with 1D Winkler beams and decoupled non-linear soil reaction springs, which is often referred to as p-y analysis. For geotechnical design, the loads applied on an offshore monopile can be simplified to equivalent loads and moments at the seabed level as shown in Figure 1, where H is the horizontal force, V is the vertical force, M is the overturning moment around a horizontal axis, T is the torsion moment around a vertical axis (M and H typically govern).

2 MONOPILE DESIGN CRITERIA

Monopile design requires the verification of the Ultimate (ULS), Serviceability (SLS) and Fatigue (FLS) limit states. For each limit state, there are one or more checks which need to be undertaken in order to verify the design.

2.1 Fatigue Limit State (FLS)

Offshore wind turbines are lightly damped, dynamically sensitive structures, where the foundation stiffness plays a major role in the global response. The natural frequencies of monopile supported wind turbines are typically close to the frequencies of loading (swell, wind, blade rotation) and are therefore typically restricted to relatively narrow ranges. The analysis of natural frequencies and fatigue (FLS) is often the determining factor for the selection of the monopile diameter (CFMS 2020).

2.2 Serviceability Limit State (SLS)

The main serviceability requirement for laterally loaded piles is that the pile deformations do not exceed some specified tolerance. For the case of monopiles, this typically involves ensuring that the permanent accumulated mudline rotation at seabed, due to the history of SLS loads applied throughout its

lifetime, does not exceed a tolerance set by the turbine manufactures. Often the total allowable rotation is taken as 0.5 degrees, with 0.25 degrees allowed for pile installation and 0.25 degrees for permanent accumulated rotation. Determining the permanent accumulated rotation, which results from soil deformations caused by cyclic wind and wave action about a non-zero mean (i.e. primarily 1-way cyclic loading) is challenging.

2.3 Ultimate Limit State (ULS)

Due to the small rotations allowed by the wind turbine manufacturers, horizontal and vertical loading can be separately verified against axial and lateral capacity. Monopile axial capacity tends to be several times higher than the vertical design loads, and therefore axial ULS checks do not govern the design. Horizontal and moment loading typically govern the ULS geotechnical checks.

Figure 45. Schematic representation of a structure on a monopile (from CFMS 2020)

Current design standards for offshore monopiles (DNV 2021a,b) require that for combined lateral loading and moment loading in ULS sufficient pile capacity shall be ensured with two requirements (DNV 2021a section 7.6.2.5):

ULS1. “The theoretical design total lateral pile resistance, which is found by vectorial integration of the design lateral resistance over the length of the pile, shall not be less than the design lateral load applied at the pile head.”

ULS2. “The lateral displacement at the pile head shall not exceed some specified limit which is defined in the corresponding design basis for example. The lateral displacement shall be calculated for the design lateral load and moment in conjunction with characteristic values of the soil resistance and soil stiffness.”

The loads should be representative of the extreme loading conditions. For the first requirement (ULS1) the design resistance, R_d , can be calculated by integration of the ultimate value of the lateral soil reaction, p_u , over the embedded length of the pile, L .

$$R_d = \int_0^L p_u(\phi'_{d}, c_{u,d}) dz$$

Note that the design values (factored) of the soil strength (friction angle, ϕ'_{d} , or undrained shear strength, $c_{u,d}$) should be used in ULS1 (see table 1 for recommended partial factors). The second requirement (ULS2) is needed as laterally loaded piles are unable to mobilise the full soil resistance along its length, as there will be points along the pile where the deflection is reversed or close to zero. ULS2 typically involves undertaking a p-y analysis using design (factored) loads but characteristic (unfactored) soil parameters, and ensuring the seabed rotation does not exceed some specified value (often taken as 1.5 or 2 degrees). In some cases, designers may choose to undertake additional p-y analysis instead of calculating ULS1. In this case, a p-y analysis can be undertaken using design loads and either design (factored) soil strength inputs for the p-y curves or using p-multipliers (i.e. reducing the strength and stiffness of each p-y curve). In practice a p-multiplier of 0.8 (=1/1.25) is often deemed sufficient to satisfy ULS1. If using more advanced analysis methods, like the PISA design method or 3DFE, care must be taken to ensure the same safety margins are maintained.

Table 1. Partial Resistance and Material Factors from DNV-ST-0126 (DNV 2021a)

Loading Mode	Analysis Method	ULS	SLS
Axial	Calculation of limit skin friction and end bearing	1.25	1.00
Lateral	Effective Stress	1.15	1.00
	Total Stress	1.25	1.00

2.4 Critical Length Criteria

The response of a laterally loaded monopile is dependent on the relative stiffness of pile and soil, which results in either flexible or rigid behaviour as shown in Figure 2. In addition to the SLS, ULS1 and ULS2 requirements, the embedded length of the pile is often dictated by a ‘critical length’ criteria. In the early days of the offshore wind industry, it was deemed

necessary to ‘rigidly clamp’ the pile toe due to the large uncertainties when determining the permanent accumulated rotation (SLS), the logic being that if the pile toe movement is zero under the most extreme load, the pile will return to vertical upon unloading (i.e. no permanent accumulate rotation).

The current design standard for offshore wind turbines DNV-ST-0126 (DNV 2021a), in section 7.6.2.5 on laterally loaded piles, offers a guidance note which suggests:

“When carrying out a single-pile analysis, it is recommended to pay attention to the lateral pile head displacements that result from the single-pile analysis and make sure that they do not become too large, e.g. by following the predicted pile head displacement as function of the pile length and making sure that the design is on the flat part of the corresponding displacement-length curve.”

Strictly following this guidance note, would essentially ensure the monopiles behave as flexible piles, a therefore have little or no permanent accumulated rotations. As pile diameters have gotten larger, this criteria was deemed unsuitable and overly conservative, but nevertheless this guidance note remains within the latest DNV standard for offshore wind turbines (DNV 2021a).

Figure 46. Comparison between the rigid and flexible behaviours of laterally loaded piles (from CFMS 2020)

The current design standard for offshore geotechnical engineering DNV-RP-C212 (DNV 2021b), offers guidance which is somewhat contradictory and less onerous. In section 4.2.2.2 on monopiles, the guidance note suggests:

“When carrying out a single-pile analysis, it is recommended to pay attention to the lateral pile head displacements that result from the single-pile analysis and make sure that they do not become too large, e.g. by monitoring the predicted lateral pile head displacement δ as function of the pile length L and making sure that the design is on the part of the corresponding δ - L curve where $d\delta/dL$ is small. A criterion on the lateral deflection of the pile head or a criterion on the rotation of the pile head about a horizontal axis will be practical. Such a criterion will not be generic, but will have to be project dependent.”

In design practice, many different critical length criteria have been proposed and are used by different designers to ensure

the monopile stability and robustness as follows. When checking the critical length criteria, designers typically use characteristic (unfactored) extreme loads and cyclic soil reaction curves.

- CLC1. The "zero-toe-kick" criteria where there is no pile toe displacement (see figure 3).
- CLC2. The "vertical-tangent" criteria where two points on the pile must have zero rotation (see figure 3).
- CLC3. The "asymptote" criteria where the pile length is increased until the pile deflection (displacement or rotation) at seabed reaches a minimum i.e. further increasing the pile length has no effect on the displacements/rotations at seabed level, as shown in figure 4 (as recommended by DNV 2021a).
- CLC4. The "asymptote+10%" criteria which involves calculating at the asymptote of the pile length-rotation curve (i.e. the rotation for a very long pile), adding 10% to the value of rotation and determining the corresponding pile length from the pile length-rotation curve (see figure 4).
- CLC5. The " $\theta - L$ slope" criteria where the slope of the pile length-seabed rotation curve is limited to some value, as shown in Figure 4 (recommended in DNV 2021b).

Figure 47. Pile Length Criteria

Figure 48. Pile Length Asymptote Criteria

3 MODEL INPUTS

In order to assess and compare the various design criteria, two simple cases are compared: (i) a homogenous loose sand with relative density of 40% and (ii) a dense sand with relative density of 80%. The comparison was undertaken using a 1D Winkler beam model implemented in Matlab. The soil reaction curves were implemented using the PISA rule-based method for sand (Burd et al. 2017, Burd et al. 2020) which requires soil unit weight, γ , relative density, D_r , and small-strain shear modulus, G_0 , as inputs. Cyclic degradation was applied to the soil reaction curves using the approach described by Prendergast et al. (2022). A saturated soil unit weight of 20 kN/m^3 was used for both analysis cases. G_0 , was estimated based on relative density using the formula proposed by Brinkgreve (2010) as shown in eq (1) and Figure 5:

$$G_0 = (60 + 68 \times D_r) \left(\frac{\sigma'_{v0}}{0.1} \right)^{0.5} \quad \text{in units of MPa} \quad (2)$$

In order to be applicable to modern wind turbines, seabed design loads were estimated based on the NREL 15MW reference turbine, in 30m water depth, including hydrodynamic loading. The estimated loads used in the analysis are provided in Table 2. In all cases analysed, a fixed pile diameter to wall thickness ratio, D/t , of 120 is used.

Table 2. Estimated monopile seabed loads for 15MW turbine

Characteristic (unfactored)	H	10	MN
	M	600	MNm
Design (factored)	H	13.5	MN
	M	810	MNm

Figure 49. Utilisation vs pile length for 10m diameter monopile in loose sand

The permanent accumulated rotation, θ_{perm} , was assessed via the formula proposed by Hettler (1981):

$$\theta_{perm} = \theta_{static}(1 + t \ln N) - \theta_{elastic} \quad (3)$$

Where θ_{static} is the rotation at seabed under the applied characteristic extreme load, $\theta_{elastic}$ is the elastic deformation found by unloading to zero along a line parallel to the initial stiffness tangent, t is a parameter representing the rate of accumulation and N is the number of equivalent load cycles at the extreme load which represents the damage from a lifetime of cyclic loading. In practice, the t parameter should be determined from cyclic laboratory testing and N determined by analysing individual load packets applied to the turbine and using accumulation laws (as described in Lapastoure et al. 2022). For simplicity and based on experience, values of $t=0.22$ and $N = 15$ were used in the analysis to conservatively represent cyclic accumulation.

Figure 50. Utilisation vs pile length for 10m diameter monopile in loose sand

4 COMPARISON OF DESIGN CRITERIA

The various criteria are compared by plotting their utilisation as a function of pile length. In practice, the criteria to be used will be agreed in advance in the basis of design. The final pile length is typically determined by the criteria which provides the longest pile length at a utilisation of 1.0.

Figure 7 shows a comparison of the utilisation for the different criteria as a function of pile length for a 10m diameter monopile in loose sand. It is evident that the SLS and CLC5 criteria result in much shorter embedment lengths compared to the other methods. CLC1,2 and 3 all require embedment lengths 15 – 20m longer than the SLS criteria.

Figure 8 shows a comparison of the utilisation for the different criteria as a function of pile length for a 8m diameter monopile in dense sand. In this case it is evident that the CLC5 criteria requires the shortest length. The SLS and CLC4 criteria require similar pile lengths while CLC1,2,3 require significantly longer pile lengths.

Figure 51. Utilisation vs pile length for 10m diameter monopile in loose sand

Figure 52. Utilisation vs pile length for 8m diameter monopile in dense sand

In order to further assess these criteria, the required pile length from each criteria is plotted as a function of pile diameter for the dense sand case in Figure 9. The SLS, CLC4 and CLC5 criteria give similar ranges of pile lengths, varying from 27 – 35m. It can be seen that for CLC1-4, increasing the pile diameter increases the required pile length due to the stiffness of the pile increasing. This is not a desired trait for a pile length criteria as increasing the pile diameter leads to less displacement and rotations (and increased safety margins). It is generally acknowledged that these CLC1-4 criteria are not suitable for large diameter monopiles. For the SLS and CLC5 criteria, increasing the pile diameter results in a smaller required embedment depth, as would be expected.

Figure 53. Comparison of required pile length from different design criteria with pile diameter for dense sand

5 CONCLUSIONS

The relatively low margin in offshore wind necessitates lean and efficient designs particularly for the foundations. This paper discusses and compares the various geotechnical design criteria which govern the monopile dimensions. It is shown that traditional pile length criteria based on ‘zero toe kick’, ‘vertical tangent’ or ‘length-rotation asymptote’ are not suitable for large diameter monopiles. The criteria based on the slope of the length-rotation offered the best criteria for robustness in addition to the SLS criteria.

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Review of cyclic models for the design of monopiles supporting offshore wind turbines

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ABSTRACT: Monopiles are the most popular foundation type for offshore wind turbines. Wind, waves and current loads are intermittent in nature and offshore wind turbines are subject to complex multi-amplitude, multi-directional loading with a high number of cycles. The effects of cyclic loading on monopile response need to be carefully and accurately accounted for to ensure safe and cost-effective design. However, to date there is no industry standard approach, and no guidance is given in DNV-ST-0126, the main design standards for offshore wind turbine foundations. Hence, this paper aims at reviewing the main types of models available in the literature, from simple semi-empirical macro-element approaches to sophisticated three-dimensional finite-element analyses. The former have gained popularity in the industry, especially at early design stage, due to their simplicity allowing of quick computation and requiring minimum input parameters.

KEY WORDS: Offshore Wind; Monopile; Geotechnical Engineering; Cyclic Loading

1 INTRODUCTION

Monopiles are large diameter open ended steel piles driven into the seabed. Monopiles have small slenderness ratios of embedded length to diameter (L/D), typically less than 6. XL monopiles up to 10 m in diameter are being considered with L/D approaching 3. They are the most popular foundation type, supporting about 80% of the offshore wind turbines installed to date in Europe (Wind Europe, 2022). This is mainly due to their simple design allowing for quick fabrication, transportation and installation.

The design of monopiles is primarily governed by lateral loading, as they sustain large wind, wave and current loads. These environmental loads are intermittent in nature and monopiles are subjected to complex multi-amplitude, multi-directional loading with a high number of cycles. Cyclic loading affects the (1) ultimate capacity, (2) unloading/reloading stiffness and (3) causes accumulation of strains. These have different effects on monopile design:

- (1) Due to the strict serviceability requirements, the ultimate capacity is often not a design driver.
- (2) Offshore wind turbines founded on monopiles are long and slender structures, making them dynamically sensitive. The foundation shall be properly designed to avoid resonance with the forcing frequencies (DNV, 2021). The forcing frequencies include wind and wave loads but most importantly the rotor speed (1P) and blade passing (3P).
- (3) Clauses 3.10.2.2 and 7.6.1.18 in DNV (2021) require limiting the accumulation of permanent monopile rotation as a result of the cyclic loading sustained through the lifetime of the structure. A limit of 0.5 degree (including 0.25 degree installation tolerance) at mudline is often suggested, although individual turbine manufacturers may allow larger tolerances.

To date there is no industry standard approach for predicting monopile cyclic response and no guidance is given in the main design standards (DNV, 2021). Hence, this paper aims at reviewing the main types of models available in the literature.

Figure 54. Monopile-soil interaction modelling methodologies after Abadie (2016).

2 REVIEW OF CYCLIC MODELS FOR MONOPILE DESIGN

Abadie (2016) distinguishes three main categories of models used in practice to predict the static response of laterally loaded pile (see Figure 54). The same categorization may be applied to cyclic loading. The models are classified depending on their complexity: three-dimensional finite element analyses (1), Winkler-type approaches (2) and macro-element models (3).

2.1 Three-dimensional finite element models

Three-dimensional finite element analyses model the soil surrounding the pile as a continuum. It allows inspection of stress and strain distributions within the soil in addition of pile deflections and internal forces. Such approaches require advanced soil constitutive and numerous input parameters. Once properly calibrated, they are regarded as the most accurate approaches but require large computation time. In recent years, undertaking 3DFE as part of the engineering design process for an offshore wind farm has become relatively routine (e.g. PISA numerical framework, Burd et al. 2020). Optimisation of the foundation design for an entire wind farm requires analyses at numerous locations for varying load conditions, foundation dimensions and soil properties, often requiring thousands of analysis cases. For this reason, relying solely on 3D FEA would be too computationally expensive.

Most constitutive models available in commercial 3DFE software are unable to capture the cyclic ratcheting behaviour of soils. One exception is the SANISAND-MS soil model (Liu et al., 2019), which was specifically tailored to model the cyclic ratcheting behaviour of sands. This model is an enhancement of SANISAND04 (Dafalias & Manzari, 2014) with addition of a memory surface accounting for the fabric effects during cyclic loading. The memory surface only requires 3 additional parameters to the standard 13 input parameters. The prediction capabilities of the SANISAND-MS soil model were demonstrated by comparison with drained (Liu et al., 2019) and undrained (Liu et al., 2020) soil element cyclic tests. Liu et al. (2021) investigated the sensitivity of monopile cyclic response to sand relative density and loading conditions using SANISAND-MS in Opensees (open source finite element package developed by Berkeley). Both one-way, partial one-way and partial two-way loading were considered with peak load ranging from 0.125% to 50% of pile ultimate capacity. The results were qualitatively compared to the 1-g laboratory experiments by Leblanc et al. (2010) and Richards et al. (2020) to showcase suitability of the approach. However, no quantitative comparison of the predicted monopile accumulated rotation was made. Only 100 cycles were considered and yet it required 49 hours to compute. Such advanced implicit constitutive soil models are very valuable for research purposes to investigate complex soil-structure interactions such as the sand densification upon lateral cyclic loading as shown on Figure 55. However, they cannot yet be realistically applied in day-to-day engineering.

Figure 55. Densification of sand after 100 load cycles investigated with SANISAND-MS soil model in OpenSees (modified after Liu, 2020). (top) $D_R^{\text{initial}} = 30\%$. (bottom) $D_R^{\text{initial}} = 70\%$.

Another constitutive model developed to capture cyclic ratcheting behaviour is the High Cycle Accumulation (HCA) model from Niemunis et al. (2005), which was developed for the accumulation of strain in sand. It can be regarded as a trade-off between implicit and explicit procedure. In implicit procedures (such as SANISAND-MS), small strain increments after each load cycle are summed to obtain final accumulated strains. Applicability of such procedures is limited by the number of cycles. Computation time can be prohibitive and small inaccuracies, inherent in finite element analysis, may accumulate and lead to large errors. Explicit procedures, where the accumulated strain is directly calculated as a function of the cycle number, are more robust and time efficient. However, they are often less accurate due to simplifications required to obtain such explicit formulations. Niemunis et al. (2005) proposed to calculate implicitly the first few load cycles using an extended hypoplasticity model (Niemunis & Herle, 1997). The rate of strain accumulation is then explicitly extrapolated for a large number of cycles, drastically reducing computation time (see Figure 56). The explicit accumulation procedure can be occasionally interrupted to implicitly calculate so-called ‘control cycles’ to update the rate of accumulation and test the admissibility of the stress state. At soil element scale, the HCA model was validated against cyclic triaxial tests by Wichtmann (2016). Settlement measurements during full scale test of a gravity base foundation for offshore wind turbines was compared to HCA prediction made by Zachert et al. (2015), validating the approach at foundation scale. Page et al. (2021) have applied the HCA model to monopile foundation showing a good match with centrifuge cyclic tests carried out by Bayton et al. (2018). Although such hybrid implicit-explicit approaches are expected to be computationally less expensive than implicit formulations, no computation times were reported. In addition, HCA is not available in any commercial 3D FEA

software. Finally, HCA requires numerous parameters that may not be easily calibrated from standard element tests.

Figure 56. Rationale of the High Cycle Accumulation model explicit formulation (Niemunis et al., 2005).

Building on their experience with soil cyclic contour diagrams, NGI (Norwegian Geotechnical Institute) developed monopile design procedures under cyclic loading applicable in finite element analysis. UDCAM (Undrained Cyclic Accumulation Model) and PDCAM (Partially Drained Cyclic Accumulation Model) were both implemented as user-defined soil models in the commercial finite element software PLAXIS 3D (Page et al., 2013). 3D contour diagrams from cyclic and monotonic triaxial and DSS tests constitute the main inputs enabling the modelling of the non-linear average and cyclic stress-strain relationship. UDCAM is applicable to clays where undrained behaviour is considered for both the average and the cyclic loads. On the contrary, PDCAM is applicable to sands where effective stress analysis (partly drained) is considered for the average load. In addition of the accumulation of shear strain, PDCAM considers the accumulation of volume deformations and pore pressures. The latter requires additional pore pressure contour diagrams. These two models are built upon the strain accumulation principle developed by NGI (Andersen, 1976). The different cyclic load packets, each of constant amplitude, are explicitly accounted for to define an equivalent number of cycles (N_{eq}) varying along and around the pile (see Figure 57). The larger N_{eq} , the more severe is the soil degradation due to cyclic loading. Jostad et al. (2014) applied UDCAM to offshore foundation design. Good prediction capabilities were demonstrated by comparison with gravity-based foundation tests reported by Dyvik et al. (1989). It is also shown that UDCAM is well suited for monopile cyclic modelling by comparison with results based on the API ‘p-y’ approach. UDCAM predicts displacements in the ULS and SLS 50% smaller than that predicted by API. It is suggested by the authors that such a procedure is much more time efficient and robust than models following each cycle, especially when a large number of cycles are considered. A simplified version of UDCAM is now generally available in PLAXIS (Plaxis, 2022).

Figure 57. UDCAM prediction of N_{eq} in the soil surrounding a cyclically laterally loaded monopile (Jostad et al., 2014).

2.2 Winkler-type approaches

Winkler-type approaches are often regarded as satisfactory compromise between accuracy and computation time. They involve modelling the pile embedment by means of one-dimensional elastic beam elements. The pile-soil interactions are captured by nonlinear soil reaction curves such as ‘p-y’ curves, predicting the soil lateral reaction, p , as a function of the pile lateral displacement, y . Winkler-type approaches allow inspection of deflection and internal forces along the entire pile embedment but give no indication of the stress and strain distribution in the soil continuum surrounding the pile. The accuracy of such approaches relies on the calibration of the soil reaction curves considered. Cyclic soil reaction curves are typically obtained by degradation of the static curves. To date, it is unclear how these can be translated into the new PISA framework for monopile design, which include additional soil reaction curves (distributed moment, base shear and base moment).

The API cyclic approach for laterally loaded piles in sands (API, 2014) consists of significantly reducing ultimate soil reaction at shallow depth. No modification to the initial stiffness of the curves is considered. The magnitude of the cyclic degradation does not account for the number of cycles applied nor the magnitude of the cyclic loading. This simplistic approach has been successfully applied for decades by the oil and gas industry, for which the focus is on conservative design against structural failure. However, monopile design optimisation requires accurate prediction of accumulated permanent rotation as a function of the cycle number.

The work carried out by SOLCYP (a four-year joint industry project on the behaviour of piles under cyclic loading) and summarised in Solcyp (2017, includes an extensive review of the literature and numerous centrifuge cyclic lateral pile tests. It resulted in a more elaborate degradation of the ‘p-y’ curves. Results suggested a reduction of the ultimate soil reaction with the number of cycles at shallow depth while deeper reactions are less affected (Figure

58). Hence, the proposed approach, termed SOLCYP-L, accounts for both the number of cycles and the load magnitude, with respect to the capacity of the pile. The degradation varies with depth and no degradation is considered below a depth of 5 times the pile diameter. The degradation parameters are applied as a p-multiplier, affecting both the ultimate capacity and initial stiffness of the curves. However, the static soil reaction curves were computed according to NF P 94-262 (AFNOR, 1997), considering only ‘p-y’ curves. The tests were carried out on rather slender flexible pile with slenderness ratio (L/D) in excess of 15. No special consideration for the load eccentricity was made, although this is a key characteristic of the lateral loading experienced by monopiles. Hence, there is no evidence of direct applicability of the SOLCYP-L for monopile design.

Figure 58. Effect of cyclic loading on p-y curves in sand (Rosquoët, 2004).

Zhang and Andersen (2017) proposed a new framework to compute site specific p-y curves directly from direct simple shear (DSS) tests in clay. Zhang et al. (2017) further developed this framework by considering cyclic loading. Based on the same approach, cyclic p-y curves can be scaled from soil DSS cyclic contour diagrams. Figure 59 presents the similarity between a laterally loaded pile element and a DSS soil element test. The ratio of mobilised soil lateral reaction upon cyclic loading over ultimate reaction (p/p_u) is considered equivalent to ratio of mobilised shear stress over undrained shear strength (τ/s_u). Such procedure requires numerous cyclic laboratory experiments to build the cyclic contour diagram and hence is only practicable for the later stages of design. The framework allows computation of site-specific soil reaction curves.

Figure 59. Analogy between pile lateral loading and Direct Simple Shear soil element test (Zhang et al. 2016).

Beuckalaers et al. (2022) have recently applied the Hyperplastic Accelerated Ratcheting Model (HARM) in a generalised Winkler model consistent with the PISA framework. HARM was originally developed for macro-element monopile modelling, as discussed in the next section. The simulated results showed good match with the PISA large scale field tests in both sand and clay (see Figure 60). It should be noted that this required the input parameters to be calibrated directly to match the field test results. The predictive capability of this approach to unseen data was not fully demonstrated.

Figure 60. Comparison of PISA large scale field tests (black line) with results simulated by HARM implemented within a Winkler-type model (red line) for Pile CM6 at the Cowden site (from Beuckelaers 2017)

2.3 Macro-element models

Macro-element models are the most simplistic approach, incorporating the interactions between the pile and the soil into surface springs. Hence, such models provide no information on structural forces nor deflections along pile embedded length. They require limited input parameters and run very quickly. However, they are often calibrated for specific soil and load conditions, making it challenging to apply them directly to a real monopile design case. Macro-element models are best suited for the early stages of monopile design.

Most of the macro-element models in the literature predict the monopile mudline cyclic deformation (displacement or rotation), θ_{cyclic} , explicitly from the cycle number, N , and from the static deformation under the same load magnitude, θ_{static} . Most models are either power (e.g. Little & Briaud, 1988, Long & Vanneste, 1994, Leblanc, 2010, Klinkvort, 2012, Roosen et al., 2013, Albiker et al., 2016, Solcyp, 2017) or logarithmic function (e.g. Hettler, 1981, Lin & Liao, 1999, Verdure et al., 2003, Li et al., 2010, Bienen et al., 2012, SOLCYP, 2017) of the cycle number and can be simplified into equation (3) or (5), respectively. The parameters t and a representing the rate of accumulation are a function of pile geometry, characteristics of the cyclic loading and site conditions. In the literature, they are broadly found to range from 0.04 to 0.25 and from 0.072 to 0.31, respectively.

Further details on the evaluation of macro element approaches for non-cohesive soils can be found in Frick and Achmus (2022).

$$\theta_{cyclic} = \theta_{static}(1 + t \ln N) \quad (4)$$

$$\theta_{cyclic} = \theta_{static}N^a \quad (5)$$

The characteristics of the cyclic loading are commonly captured by two parameters as per Figure 61. The lateral load, H , applied at an eccentricity, e , above mudline corresponds to an overturning moment at mudline, $M=H \times e$. Hence, ζ_b and ζ_c in equations (6) and (7) are expressed in terms of H or M where relevant. ζ_b characterises the magnitude of the cyclic loading (H_{max} or M_{max}) with respect to the pile lateral capacity (H_{ult} or M_{ult}). ζ_c characterises the direction of the cyclic loading: one-way ($\zeta_c = 0$), partial one-way ($0 < \zeta_c < 1$), two-way ($\zeta_c = -1$) or partial two-way ($-1 < \zeta_c < 0$).

$$\zeta_b = \frac{H_{max}}{H_{ult}} = \frac{M_{max}}{M_{ult}} \quad (6)$$

$$\zeta_c = \frac{H_{min}}{H_{max}} = \frac{M_{min}}{M_{max}} \quad (7)$$

Figure 61. Characteristic of cyclic loading (Leblanc, 2010).

The following points discuss some of the uncertainties / contradictions between different research:

- All researchers agreed that the two extreme cases ($\zeta_c = -1$ and $\zeta_c = 1$) lead to no accumulation of cyclic rotation (i.e. $a = 0$ or $t = 0$). However, there is no consensus for the intermediate cases.
- Most researchers found pure one-way loading to be the most detrimental. However, Leblanc (2010) and Klinkvort (2012) found the intermediate case $\zeta_c = -0.6$ to be the most detrimental.
- Similarly, although most researchers found the rate of accumulation to increase with ζ_b , there is no consensus on how to define monopile lateral capacity. For example, Leblanc (2010) defines capacity for a mudline rotation of 4 degrees, a limit of 2 degrees or 10% pile diameter were used during the PISA project, Albiker et al. (2016) used approximately 3 degrees, Verdure et al. (2003) considered a tangent-asymptote approach leading to about 1 pile diameter, SOLCYP (2017) considered a slightly different tangent approach for their global model (SOLCY-G) leading to about 25% pile diameter, etc. Such disparity makes comparison of the different models and experimentations rather challenging.

- Another concern is whether the approach predicts accumulated pile displacement or rotation. Most of the explicit models mentioned were developed for accumulation of pile displacement. Rotation is more relevant for monopile design given the strict 0.25 degrees limit specified in DNV (2021). Hence, it is a common practice in the industry to use the same formulation for rotation. However, Li et al. (2015) shows that accumulated rotation and displacement can both be depicted with log or power functions, but parameters will not be the same. Only more recently, Leblanc et al. (2010), Klinkvort (2012) and Albiker et al. (2016) carried out 1-g or centrifuge laboratory experiments specifically for monopiles, looking at accumulated rotation and taking care to use relevant pile geometry (small L/D) and load eccentricities (couple of diameters above soil surface).
- Another disparity is whether the model aims at predicting the maximum (loaded) or permanent (unloaded) rotation. Most explicit models predict the maximum rotation accumulated through the cyclic loading. Cuéllar (2011) found that a loglinear fit better the evolution of the permanent rotation with number of cycles. If the maximum rotation is predicted, it is critical to estimate how much the rotation reduces upon unloading. Although some researchers reported increasing unloading-reloading stiffness upon cyclic loading, the static stiffness is usually conservatively considered. The unloading might be done following the initial linear stiffness or assuming Masing's rule as discussed by Prendergast & Igoe (2022).
- Finally, all these models concern a single load package. However, the monopiles experience multi-direction, multi-amplitude cyclic loading through their lifetime. Hence, based on Miner's strain superposition, researchers have developed approaches to define a number of cycles, N_{eq} , equivalent of the entire cyclic load history. However, different researchers used different variables of interest to define N_{eq} . For example, DGGT (2013) considers the total cyclic rotation to remain constant at the end of load packet and at the beginning of the next one. This is disregarding the instant change of pile rotation due to the increase of the lateral loading from one load packet to the next one. Hence, Leblanc et al. (2010) considered a constant increase due to cyclic loading (see Figure 62 where $\Delta\theta = \theta_{cyclic} - \theta_{static}$). Another approach suggested by Page et al. (2021) involves considering constant accumulated permanent rotation. The effect of different accumulation models is discussed in detail in Lapastoure et al. (2022).

The French committee for soil mechanics and geotechnics (CFMS, 2020) recommends three macro-element models for modelling the pile response: (i) the Hettler (1981) model; (ii) the Leblanc et al. (2010) model and (iii) the models developed by Solcyp (2017). EA-Pfähle (DGGT, 2013), the German recommendations for piling, recommends the model developed by Hettler (1981) to predict the deflection accumulation of piles subjected to cyclic lateral loading. These are the most likely to be used by industry, especially at the early stages of design. Due to their simplicity, macro-

element models allow for quick computation and require minimum design inputs.

Figure 62. Superposition theory for accumulation of cyclic rotation from one load package to another (Leblanc et al. 2010b)

Another macro-element model suggested by CFMS (2021) is the Hyperplastic Accelerated Ratcheting Model (HARM) developed by Houlsby and co-workers at Oxford (Houlsby et al., 2017; Abadie et al., 2019). HARM has been specially developed to study the monopile's response to cyclic loading. The model is derived from the hyper elasticity framework and provides a 0-D representation of the soil-pile macro response. It has been developed based on a series of specifically designed 1-g laboratory scale model tests in sand. Up to 100,000 cycles were applied to identify key mechanisms of pile response to cyclic loading. Among other observations, the experimental results showed an accumulation of pile deformation whose rate decreases with the number of cycles but always remains non-null. It was also shown that the cyclic hysteresis loops tend to tighten with an increased secant stiffness and decreased loop area. Finally, the extended Masing rule seems to apply as the pile static response after a cyclic loading history tends towards the initial static response. HARM is able to replicate the complete pile macro response to complex cyclic loading in terms of load-displacement curves as shown in Figure 63. The model showed good predictions of not only the accumulation of pile displacement but also the secant stiffness increase, and hysteresis loop area decrease with increasing number of cycles. In order to reduce the computation time, the author implemented an accelerated procedure. A high number of identical cycles can be simulated by a reduced number of equivalent cycles. Although this framework seems to mark a significant step forward in the modelling of monopile response to cyclic loading, it has only been validated against small scale laboratory piles. Additional features such as gap formation between the pile and the soil may need to be implemented for the model to be applied to

large scale monopiles. Finally, even if the model has the advantage of being computationally efficient, it requires an extensive calibration exercise, which is not easy to undertake. While the HARM model offers considerable promise, it is not yet used in industry for the design of monopiles, primarily due to the challenges in calibrating the model.

Figure 63. Comparison of experimental and HARM predicted load-displacement curves for complex cyclic loading. (Abadie, 2016).

3 CONCLUSION

Capturing the effects of cyclic loading on monopile response is critical for offshore wind turbine foundation design. However, there is no industry standard approach, and no guidance is given in the main design standards (DNV, 2021). Hence, this paper aims at reviewing the main types of models available in the literature. The models are classified depending on their complexity: three-dimensional finite-element analyses (1), Winkler-type approaches (2) and macro-element models (3).

- (1) Three-dimensional finite-element analyses model the soil surrounding the pile as a continuum. They allow inspection of stress and strain distributions within the soil in addition to pile deflections and internal forces. Such approaches require advanced soil constitutive models and numerous input parameters. Once properly calibrated, they are regarded as the most accurate approaches but require large computation time. This is specifically true for implicit models such as SANISAND-MS which may only be suitable for research purposes. Explicit models such as HCA or UDCAM/PDCAM have been developed in order to limit computation time and hence may be suitable to verify design at later stages.
- (2) Winkler-type approaches are often regarded as a satisfactory compromise between accuracy and computation time. They allow inspection of deflection and internal forces along the pile but give no indication of the stress and strain distribution in the soil continuum. The accuracy of such approaches relies on the calibration of the soil reaction curves considered. Since it is now widely acknowledged that the traditional API approach is not suitable for monopile design, numerous research efforts have been carried out to define cyclic soil reaction curves. Some approaches require minimum inputs (e.g. SOLCYP-L) and may be used at the early stages of design while others require

advanced laboratory tests (e.g. Zhang & Andersen) making them more suitable at later stages.

- (3) Macro-element models are the most simplistic approach, incorporating the interactions between the pile and the soil into surface springs. They require limited input parameters and run very quickly making them ideal candidates for early stages of design. However, the numerous logarithmic and power accumulation laws proposed in the literature have been calibrated for very specific conditions. They often lead to very different results when applied to a specific design case. Recently, the more advanced HARM model has been proposed and seems promising, but it lacks a suitable calibration process to be used as part of the foundation design process.

EA-Pfähle, the German recommendations for piling, recommends the model developed by Hettler (1981) to predict the deflection accumulation of piles subjected to cyclic lateral loading. The French committee for soil mechanics and geotechnics (CFMS, 2020) also recommends Hettler's model as well as models developed by SOLCYP (2017) and Leblanc et al. (2010). The three of them are macro-element models. They are the most likely to be used by the industry, especially at the early stages of design.

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Use of shear wave velocity (V_s) to characterise offshore glacial tills

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ABSTRACT: Many of the future wind farms offshore Ireland will encounter glacial tills. This will be the case not only for the foundations for the offshore turbines but also to anchorages for floating offshore wind turbines as well as cable routes and pipelines. Traditionally the main tool used to characterise offshore soils is the cone penetration test (CPT / CPTU). A particular characteristic of the Irish tills, say when compared to similar material in the UK, is the presence of large cobbles and boulders. These make in situ investigation using the CPT extremely difficult. In parallel there have been significant developments in the measurement of shear wave velocity (V_s) offshore using cost effective surface wave methods such as MASW (multi-channel analysis of surface waves) or using optic fibre / distributed acoustic sensing (DAS) techniques. It would now seem that V_s profiles can be relatively easily and reliably obtained. In this paper the link between strength and stiffness from high quality laboratory tests on cores and V_s measurements at several onshore sites will be explored to investigate the potential of using V_s to profile the general characteristics as well as the undrained shear strength and stiffness of Irish offshore tills.

KEY WORDS: Cone penetration testing; shear wave velocity; offshore; undrained shear strength; glacial tills

1 INTRODUCTION

Cone penetration testing (CPT) or testing with pore water pressure measurement (CPTU) is the fundamental tool used to characterise the engineering properties of seabed soils. In CPTU testing typically a 10 cm² or 15 cm² instrumented cone is pushed at a standard rate of 2 cm/sec into the seabed and the cone end resistance (q_c), sleeve friction (f_s) and pore water pressure (usually u_2) are logged continuously. CPT testing was first carried out offshore in 1972 (Lunne 2012) with CPTU tests following shortly afterwards. Over the years the measured parameters have been used to characterise the seabed soils, to obtain the relevant design parameters such as strength and stiffness and are now frequently used directly in design (of for example piling) without an initial conversion being required into a soil property. It has been used successfully in deposits such as the dense sands of the North Sea, the soft clays of the Gulf of Mexico and the calcareous sediments offshore Western Australia. It can deliver reliable, high-resolution, geotechnical profiling to depths of up to 50 m below the seabed to International Standards Organisation (ISO) standards (ISO 2012). It is understood that this standard is soon to be updated.

Until recently CPTU data was always backed up with some sampling and laboratory testing. However confidence in CPTU is now such that it is often used in isolation. Andersen et al. (2008) reviewed the use of CPTU in the design of various offshore infrastructure schemes and in the selection of the relevant design parameters and concluded that CPTU “has been and is the main testing tool”.

There is no doubt that CPTU will form an essential part of renewable energy developments in the Irish offshore. All international designers and contractors will consider these data as critical to the work.

Figure 2. Bent CPTU rod and sheared cone.

However, the advance of the British and Irish Ice Sheet (BIIS) during the last glaciation covered much of the continental shelf depositing a range of material, including glacial till (ÓCofaigh & Evans 2001; Scourse et al. 2021). Although relatively poorly sampled offshore Ireland, these glacial tills are dense and stony in nature (Jackson et al. 1995) with the result that the CPT is often unable to penetrate significant depths into the strata. An example from some work acquired in the vicinity of Dundalk Bay in 2014 onboard the RV Celtic Explorer, using the University of Bremen developed Geotechnical Offshore Seabed Tool (GOST) system, is shown on Figure 1a (Coughlan et al. 2022). Only limited CPTU data is available here as no f_s and u_2 data were recorded. The corrected cone resistance (q_t) values confirm that the material is highly competent with q_t increasing rapidly with depth up to about 18 MPa when the CPTU refused at 3.25 m.

Further efforts at acquiring CPTU data in these glacial deposits were undertaken in 2022 onboard the RV Celtic Explorer using the Geomil Manta-200, a significantly heavier system of approximately 18t, and still issues were encountered including rod-bending as the cone struggled to push through the till (Figure 2).

Similarly, during site investigations at the Dogger Bank Offshore Wind Farm site, dense to very dense sands and very stiff clays associated with past glacial conditions were encountered that required the development of an enhanced CPT system (Yetginer-Tjelta et al. 2022).

Figure 64. Some (a) CPT and (b) UMASW data for Irish Sea site in the vicinity of Dundalk Bay (Coughlan et al. 2022)

The primary objective of a site investigation is to gather data with which to assess ground conditions before undertaking development works. To that end, there are a number of different survey techniques, each providing different types of data, with the CPT considered the primary tool and various guidance notes provided with regards to offshore renewable energy development. Given the challenges that exist in acquiring CPT data in these Irish offshore glacial tills, the objective of this paper is to assess geophysical methods, such as multichannel analysis of surface waves (MASW), that can be used to characterise these deposits for engineering projects. In addition, comparisons with onshore analogues are made to better understand the nature of offshore deposits and their potential characteristics

2 METHODS USED

2.1 MASW and UMASW

MASW is a non-invasive technique which allows estimation of seismic shear wave velocity (V_s). Surface waves are seismic waves that travel along a boundary between two media, which can be of gas, liquid or solid-state. If the interface is between gas and solid the surface wave is of Rayleigh type, which is the wave under consideration when performing MASW on land.

This technique was introduced in the late 1990s by the Kansas Geological Survey (Park et al. 1999). The method utilises the dispersion property of surface waves for the purpose of V_s profiling in 1D (depth) or 2D (depth and surface location) format. The entire procedure for MASW usually consists of four steps, see Figure 3a.

- (1) Acquire field records by using a multichannel recording system and a receiver array deployed over a few hundred meters of distance, like those used in conventional seismic reflection surveys. Typically, in geotechnical work the test configuration comprises twenty-four geophones spaced at 3 m centres over the survey length. An impulsive source (e.g. a sledgehammer) is used to generate the surface waves.

- (2) Use is then made of the dispersive properties of the soil; i.e. longer wavelength signals reflect the deeper soils and shorter wavelengths represent the shallower soils, to produce a phase velocity versus wavelength relationship from the measured data.
- (3) This phase velocity versus wavelength trace is converted to a dispersion curves (phase velocity versus frequency). Usually fundamental mode dispersion only is used.
- (4) The dispersion curve is inverted to obtain 1D (depth) V_s profiles (one profile from one curve). The inversion process involves the user specifying a synthetic ground profile (number of layers as well as the density, V_s and Poisson ratio of each layer) and the software then iterates until the synthetic and field dispersion curves match. The software tool mostly used in Ireland for the purpose of inversion is Surfseis (Park & Brohammer 2003).

However, when moving offshore, the interface is between water and an elastic solid (soil), which means the surface wave is no longer of Rayleigh type but is now a Scholte wave or Stoneley-Scholte wave. Scholte waves have a similar particle motion and dispersive nature to that of Rayleigh waves, but they propagate at 88% to 99% of the Rayleigh wave velocity, depending on the thickness of the water layer.

McGrath et al. (2016) presented the results of an MASW survey carried out of the east coast of Dublin, Ireland, comparing the measurements of V_s of both onshore and offshore (UMASW) in the intertidal zone, along with seismic cone testing (SCPTU) on this site. The results of the tests indicate that hydrophones at the bottom of a water column can produce surface wave data of similar quality to that produced by geophones on land. The source used is an air gun rather than a sledgehammer.

Tests using the same equipment has since been completed in water depths of up to 50 m off the west coast of Ireland where the environmental conditions are much harsher (Long et al. 2020).

Figure 3. (a) MASW. Image from Donohue (2005) and (b) SCPTU. Image from Butcher & Powell (1995)

2.2 SCPTU

A standard cone penetrometer is equipped generally with two horizontally aligned seismic sensors (Figure 3b). The seismic signals are only recorded during pauses in penetration, commonly every 0.5 or 1.0 m. A horizontal beam coupled to the ground surface by the weight of the testing vehicle is the source of the seismic energy. The beam is struck on end with a hammer to generate horizontally polarized vertically propagating shear waves that can be detected by the horizontal receiver within the cone penetrometer embedded below. The velocity is determined from the travel-time differences between recorded waves at the two sensors and the difference in the assumed travel path lengths.

2.3 Distributed Acoustic Sensing

Recently spatially extensive V_s data have been reliably determined based on Distributed Acoustic Sensing (DAS) of optic fibres laid on the sea bed (Trafford et al. 2021). Subsequently Trafford et al. (2022b) found that the DAS system was effective in rapidly determining the V_s profiles in a variety of geological conditions near Dundalk Bay. The system is described in detail in a companion paper to this conference by Trafford et al. (2022a).

3 V_s PROFILES

3.1 Shear wave velocity – basics

V_s is a fundamental measurement in all solids for example steel, concrete, wood, soil and rock (Mayne 2000). Because of this broad range of application, V_s values are an attractive means of characterising a range of natural geomaterials. Water is not able to tolerate shear waves. Therefore measurements in soil are not influenced by the presence of groundwater (unlike P-waves).

Engineer's interest in V_s determination has largely been driven by the need to obtain values of the small strain shear modulus (G_{max}), as this is an important parameter for a range of geotechnical design applications. This usually involves strains of 10^{-4} to 10^{-3} % and less. According to elastic theory G_{max} may be calculated from the shear wave velocity using the following equation:

$$G_{max} = \rho V_s^2 \quad (1)$$

where: G_{max} is the shear modulus (in Pa), V_s is in m/s, and ρ is the total mass density (in kg/m^3).

It is important to remember that for practical use, the G_{max} value needs to be reduced to give the strain level relevant to a particular problem.

3.2 Anisotropy

Anisotropy of shear wave velocity / stiffness may be significant in many clays. This is particularly the case for overconsolidated materials. Butcher and Powell (Butcher & Powell 1995) and others have suggested that to distinguish

between shear wave velocities with different propagation and polarisation directions, subscripts can be used to denote these.

For example V_{s-vh} denotes a vertically propagating, horizontally polarised shear wave velocity such as would be measured in a downhole or SCPTU test. Similarly V_{s-hv} or V_{s-hh} would be measured in cross-hole testing.

3.3 V_s of onshore tills

3.3.1 Dublin boulder clay

Much of the ground engineering work carried out in Ireland involves glacial tills. These tills were deposited beneath the ice sheet that covered much of Ireland during the Pleistocene period, some 18,000 years ago. For example, much of the city of Dublin it is underlain by a glacial deposit known colloquially as Dublin Boulder Clay (DBC). It was known that the ice thickness in Dublin was approximately 1 km and that several advances and retreats of the glaciers occurred in the area. The grinding action of this sheet as it eroded the underlying rocks coupled with its loading effect resulted in the formation of a hard lodgement till which in engineering terms is characterised by being very dense / hard, of very high stiffness and of low permeability. The geological origin, and classification of the DBC as well as its engineering parameters have been well researched (Farrell & Wall 1990), (Long & Menkiti 2007), (Skipper et al. 2005).

A particular characteristic of the Irish tills, say when compared to similar material in the UK, is the presence of large cobbles and boulders. These make in situ investigation and sampling of the material extremely difficult. Hence there has been an interest in non-intrusive geophysical techniques, such as MASW, to help characterize the materials.

Some V_s profiles for DBC obtained from MASW testing are shown on Figure 4.

Figure 4. V_s profiles for Dublin boulder clay. Data extended from that given by Long & Menkiti (2007) with additional data courtesy of Paul Quigley (IGSL) and Miles Friedman (TII)

The values fall in a relative tight band with V_s increasing from typically 300 m/s at the ground surface to 700m/s at 12m depth. These are very high values. For example Poulos (2021) suggests that clays with V_s greater than 360 m/s can be classified as “hard”. The values for DBC are closer to those of a weak rock.

3.3.2 Other onshore Irish tills

A similar set of data for a range of Irish glacial tills from areas other than Dublin are shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. V_s profiles for Irish glacial tills other than DBC. Data courtesy Paul Quigley (IGSL)

It can be seen that, for the most part, the values fall within the upper and lower bounds established for DBC. An exception is perhaps the Kerry site where the V_s values are a little lower. However in the upper 3 m, where lab test data is available, the values fall within the range for DBC.

Also shown on Figure 5 is an UMASW profile from Dundalk Bay (Coughlan et al. 2022). The same profile is shown on Figure 1b where it is illustrated that, although the CPT test refused at about 3.25 m, the UMASW profile extended to 28 m depth. Here the geological history and provenance of the glacial tills is different from onshore Ireland with extensive reworking of sediment by the Irish Sea Ice Stream (ISIS) offshore and episodes of ice sheet readvance likely causing overconsolidation in certain areas.

The V_s values are much lower than those measured onshore with V_s increasing from about 200 m/s at the seabed to 400 m/s at 20 m depth. These values suggest the material is initially firm becoming stiff and very stiff with depth.

3.3.3 Eastern UK tills

Available data for UK glacial tills is shown on Figure 6. The data is from the eastern side of the UK and for the most part is from SCPTU tests though some cross-hole data is available from the Cowden research site. The profiles fall in a narrow band and the values are much lower than for the Irish tills.

V_s varies generally about 200 m/s at ground level to some 400m/s at 25 m depth, i.e. are very similar to the offshore Irish till. These lower values are consistent with the knowledge that the Irish tills have much higher strength and stiffness and a significantly higher stone content. The clasts in the Irish tills are generally made of much stronger rocks compared to the chalk and similar rocks found in the UK tills.

Figure 6. V_s profiles for Eastern UK tills. Data from Powell & Butcher (2003), Zdravkovic et al. (2020), Brown et al. (2006) and Baker (1988)

3.4 Anisotropy of V_s

The anisotropy of stiffness of DBC can be assessed by comparing results of MASW and cross-hole testing as shown on Figure 7. It can be seen that for the three sites under study the values measured are more or less the same for the two techniques indicating the degree of anisotropy is very low.

A similar set of data for Cowden till is shown on Figure 8. Here it can be seen that the till possesses a degree of stiffness anisotropy with V_{s-hh} values being significantly higher than V_{s-vh} especially down to 10 m.

These findings are of significance in the design of offshore monopile foundations, for example, where the horizontal stiffness rather than the vertical stiffness is the key input parameter. These data suggest that for onshore Irish tills at least surface wave testing will give the required design parameters without resort to more expensive cross-hole testing. More work is needed on offshore Irish tills.

Figure 7. V_s profiles for DBC from MASW and cross hole testing. Data from (Donohue et al. 2003)

Figure 8. V_s profiles for Cowden till. Data from Powell & Butcher (2003)

4 CORRELATIONS BETWEEN V_s AND S_u

4.1 General

Much work has been done in the past in correlating V_s with various soil properties derived from laboratory testing. An important consideration is that, for the correlation to be reliable, the quality of the soil samples must be very high. To that end in this paper soil samples extracted only by high quality samplers, such as the Geobore-S, will be considered.

Many empirical V_s -undrained shear strength (s_u) relationships can be found in the literature. Long (2022) suggests that at least 20 such relationships exist.

Undrained shear strength has no unique value but depends on the age of the sample, test type, rate of loading, anisotropy and other factors. Therefore comparisons can only be made on results of tests carried out on exactly the same manner.

4.2 Irish tills

Long & Menkiti (2007) compared the engineering quality of Geobore-S cores to hand carved block samples from the site of the Dublin Port Tunnel and found them to be very similar. An interesting finding from this work was that if high quality cores were available then the s_u measured in sophisticated CIUC or CAUC (isotropically or anisotropically consolidated undrained) triaxial compression tests was very similar to that obtained from relatively simple UU (unconsolidated undrained) testing.

Figure 9. V_s versus s_u for Irish glacial tills. Plot modified from that in Long et al. (2013)

V_s from MASW and undrained shear strength (s_u) from triaxial tests on the high quality rotary cores of various Irish glacial tills are shown on Figure 9. Data from twelve sites is presented. Eight of these are from the Dublin area. These data are complimented by four others from throughout Ireland. As can be seen V_s values in the range 200 m/s to 1100 m/s are encompassed. As shown, there is a reasonably strong relationship between s_u and V_s with s_u increasing with increasing V_s . The coefficient of correlation for the trend line shown is about 0.87. Beyond a V_s of about 400 m/s the relationship appears to be more or less linear.

4.3 UK tills

A similar set of data for UK glacial tills is shown on Figure 10. Here V_s from SCPTU testing (i.e. V_{s-vh}) is used. There is significant scatter in the data. The trendline derived for the Irish till (Figure 9) underestimates the s_u of the till at the Cowden and Pisa sites but overestimates that for the Grimsby site. Further work is required on this topic and it is consistent with the finding of Long (2022) who showed that correlations developed for one area do not always apply to other areas. Ideally local correlations should be developed.

Figure 10. V_{s-vh} versus s_u for Eastern UK glacial tills. Data from same sources as that in Figure 6.

5 CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Recent practical experience during CPT data acquisition offshore Ireland has highlighted the challenges posed by glacial tills. This has resulted in limited data collection in deposits that are planned to support future offshore wind turbine foundations. These glacial deposits in the north Irish Sea, exhibit a high degree of vertical and lateral heterogeneity and contain material above gravel grade, including cobbles and boulders.

The use of MASW / UMASW has been proven effective in characterising such deposits onshore and providing V_s profiles can be used as part of geotechnical design. Initial work offshore under the Sustainable Energy Authority of Ireland (SEAI) funded DeSIRE has shown promise in the similar application of MASW offshore. Given the need for flexible and effective methods for completing complex offshore site

investigations, MASW should be considered as a tool for providing reliable data in these settings. Further work is needed to develop robust correlations between V_s and CPTU derived parameters as well as with other geotechnical parameters for Irish offshore tills.

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Innovative weather downtime assessment tool (WDAT) for offshore operations

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ABSTRACT: Weather downtime is a major factor in any offshore operation as it affects both the project program and budget. Therefore, knowledge of potential weather downtime for a given site is valuable for all offshore operations undertaken by developers and contractors. This paper presents the development of a novel tool that enables a reliable and quick assessment of weather downtime for any offshore site.

With the net-zero target, there is global demand for the renewables sector to grow rapidly. In offshore wind, this would mean the development and construction of large numbers of offshore wind farms. Contractors building wind farms are interested in periods when the weather is below the allowable working limits to ensure efficient operations. One method of assessing weather downtime is to perform a statistical analysis of the historical records of metocean parameters. Obtaining such records is challenging, especially in areas where there has previously been limited human activity. The European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) developed ERA5 which is a state-of-the-art, open-source climate reanalysis database, providing hourly estimates of several atmospheric, land and oceanic climate variables on a global grid, but accessing it can be time consuming and cumbersome.

This paper presents a methodology for assessing weather downtime at a particular site for offshore operations using available ERA5 data and vessel operational specifications. The methodology is implemented in an in-house tool known as “GDG-WDAT” that is capable of interacting with the ERA5 database, enabling selective downloads for any particular site across the globe. The tool also assesses the weather downtime for any given period in a year based on given vessel operational limits providing highly valuable information to offshore wind farm developers, contractors and maintenance providers. The output from the GDG-WDAT tool enables effective operational planning and leads to considerable cost savings in offshore operations. This paper presents insights into the working principles of how weather downtime is assessed within the tool together with some practical illustrative examples.

KEY WORDS: Hindcast time-series, metocean data, offshore operations, weather downtime assessment, workability, statistical analysis

1 INTRODUCTION

Weather downtime (WDT) is a major factor in any offshore operation as it affects both the project program and budget. It can be defined as the time, or percentage of time, that operations will not be performed due to weather conditions being above predefined operational limits. Therefore, knowledge of potential weather downtime for a given site is valuable for all offshore operations undertaken by developers and contractors, from the early stages of project surveys through to the construction and operations phase.

Interest in estimating WDT dates back to the beginnings of offshore Oil & Gas exploration. One of the first studies of WDT for commercial operations was carried on in the late 1960s where McCarron (1968) and McCarron (1971) presented an investigation into the effects of weather on the construction of offshore pipelines by using a computer simulation program. The interest in estimating WDT continued in the 1970's in the works of Rawstron and Blight (1977), Springett (1977), Springett and Abramovich (1978) and Graham (1982), when the oil companies significantly reduced their spending on oil exploration offshore and the market experienced a significant increase in the number of semisubmersibles.

Other industries became interested in WDT to plan their operations, e.g. van der Wal and de Boer (2004) investigated WDT assessment methods applicable to dredging projects. More recently, with accelerated development of the offshore wind industry, the estimation of WDT became a focus of interest due to the seasonality of the works, increased repetitiveness of work tasks, and a more urgent need for cost-competitiveness than in the Oil & Gas industry, Leontaris (2015), Rip (2015), Kikuchi and Ishihara (2016), Lambkin et al. (2019), and Hudson (2019).

It should be noted that historically, one of the biggest challenges was to obtain the metocean data, as measurements were either not available, or very limited. Many research papers in the past concentrated on this problem. More recently Leontaris (2015) used mathematical methods to generate a number of weather time series from a limited amount of historical data. However, with recent advances in weather modelling and the possibility of creating hindcast time series for many years utilising the ERA5 database, the focus is switching to creating more sophisticated models for WDT assessment. Furthermore, historical data are now more readily available since the emergence of satellite-based wave measurements.

This paper presents an innovative methodology for assessing weather downtime at any offshore site using available ERA5 data and vessel operational specifications. The methodology is implemented in an in-house tool known as "GDG-WDAT" that is capable of interacting with the ERA5 database, enabling selective downloads for any particular site across the globe.

2 METOCEAN DATA

The most important weather parameters for WDT assessment are the wind speed (V_w), significant wave height (H_s), wave peak period (T_p), and steady current speed (V_c). Out of these parameters, the wind speed and significant wave height are

mostly used for WDT assessment, and are publicly available (e.g. in the ERA5 database).

The current speed, which has a crucial impact on WDT in many areas of offshore wind farm development, is often not available before detailed metocean assessment studies financed by the developer are carried out. Other parameters that may be used for WDT assessment are wind, waves and current directions.

In this work the hindcast time series figures are used, to provide the values of metocean parameters for every hour, which is the most commonly used data for WDT assessment.

For most preliminary metocean assessments, the data for European sites is obtained from Copernicus. Copernicus is EU's Earth Observation programme and offers information about climate variables from satellite Earth Observations and in-situ data. Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) and European Centre of for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) maintain an online database for worldwide historical reanalysis data. This is an open source database that allows its users to access global climate data.

3 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction

This paper presents a methodology for assessing weather downtime at a particular site for offshore operations using available ERA5 data and vessel operational specifications. The methodology is implemented in an in-house tool known as "GDG-WDAT" that is capable of interacting with the ERA5 database, enabling selective downloads for any particular site across the globe, see Figure 1. The tool also assesses the weather downtime for any given period in a year based on given vessel operational limits.

Figure 1. Working principle of developed "GDG-WDAT" tool

3.2 Publicly Available Hindcast Time-series

ERA5 reanalysis dataset is used for this study. ERA5 is a fifth generation ECMWF reanalysis dataset for the past five to seven decades. The specific database queried for this analysis is called ERA5 hourly data on single levels from 1979 to present. It provides hourly averaged estimates for a large number of atmospheric, ocean-wave and land-surface variables. It has a resolution of $0.25^\circ \times 0.25^\circ$ for wind related variables and $0.5^\circ \times 0.5^\circ$ for ocean-wave variables.

The data is packed in *netcdf* files and provided to the user for download. The data however, cannot be downloaded in a single go and needs to be broken up in several files. This is a special protocol established by ECMWF servers to manage and control the requests that come in. This however, makes

the entire process of downloading the data quite cumbersome and time consuming as a 40 year dataset will then need to be broken up into 40 different files and 40 different requests have to be put in.

For the convenience of the users, ECMWF has provided a basic Python based API to download data from the server without having to manually select each item. This again suffers from the same problem of having to run the code 40 times to download a 40 year dataset.

A unique algorithm based on the API provided by ECMWF which is able to launch several requests simultaneously has been developed in house at GDG. This algorithm allows conveniently accessing the data for the coordinates of relevance and for the duration required with a simple excel sheet without having to manually launch 40 different requests.

Part of this same algorithm is an automated file handling and data extraction component which quickly unpacks the *netcdf* files into human readable text files and passes the relevant information to the weather downtime tool in the format required for by the tool.

3.3 WDT Assessment Methodology

The WDT assessment methods are based on statistical analysis of weather data compared with the operational limits of the vessel, where the weather time series is mapped into a binary workability sequence marked as “1” if below the limit (workable) and “0” if above the limit (non-workable) at each discrete data point (most often at every hour).

WDT assessment provides information on the time (usually given as percentage, hours or days) lost during the offshore operations due to bad weather, i.e. due to weather above the operational limits of the vessel. The time to complete the operation without any weather delays is termed net operational duration and total time required to complete the operations (including weather delays) is defined as gross operational time.

The workability of the vessel is defined by the percentage of the gross operational time the weather is below the operational limits. Naturally, the offshore wind farm (OWF) sites represent a challenging environment for offshore operations, as they are chosen to maximise the energy yield. During wind assessment studies, the focus is on the time the wind is above a certain threshold whereas during construction the interest is in knowing the time the wind is below a certain threshold.

There are three widely used methods for WDT assessment, as described by Rip (2015):

- **Joint probability distribution/wave scatter** (also termed *occurrence* by Hudson (2019) or *exceedance* (or non-exceedance) by Lambkin et al. (2019) – best applicable to continuous operations, e.g. geophysical surveys and dredging. Weather parameters (e.g. wind speed and significant wave height) are checked against the operational limit of the vessel for each data point (normally for every hour) and exceedance or non-exceedance statistics are obtained. The principle of this method is presented in Figure 2, where only assessment of the H_s is presented. The same principle is applied to all limiting parameters (e.g. wind and current speed) and the final evaluation will be scored as “1” only if all parameters are “1”

in the particular hour. The downtime risk is represented by a percentage.

- **Empirical persistency distribution** – or weather windows (here defined as the time period of exceedance or non-exceedance that persists for at least a given duration), applicable to geotechnical surveys and cable installation mentioned in Lambkin et al (2019). This method uses the results from the above point, with an additional requirement of having a given number of “1” uninterruptedly. The downtime risk is represented by the exceedance distributions of weather windows or waiting time.

- **Simulation based approach** – suitable for complex projects (e.g. installation of wind turbines), where an installation programme is simulated many times using the historical weather data (or hindcast time series data) as a basis for statistical analysis. It is based on the two previous methods, but each operation may be characterised with a different weather limit and required weather window.

Figure 2. The principle of mapping the wave height record into a binary workability sequence

The working principle of the above three methods is presented in Figure 3, where A - Sample evaluation; B - Joint probability distribution/wave scatter results; C - Empirical persistency distribution results for the required weather window (WW) duration of 4hrs, overlapping; D - Empirical persistency distribution results for the required WW duration of 4hrs, non-overlapping; E-K is for simulation based methods; E - Evaluation for Activity 1; F - Operational time for activity 1 (WW = 4hrs); G - Evaluation for Activity 2; H - Operational time for activity 2 (WW = 2hrs); I - Evaluation for Activity 3; J - Operational time for activity 3 (WW = 8hrs); K - Project duration time.

Note that for a simulation based approach, the procedure has to be repeated for the same starting point in a year for a number of years to get the empirical cumulative distribution function (ECDF). The larger number of years with hindcast time series is better for a more reliable ECDF, Lambkin et al. (2019) recommended 15 – 20 years, but note that 30 – 40 years is preferable, while van der Wal and de Boer (2004) mentioned 6-10 job realisations (years) gave a reasonable estimate of the mean duration in their example.

It is important to notice the difference between overlapping and non-overlapping assessments. Overlapping assessment may be used for continuous operations like surveys or for planning access to offshore assets for maintenance. However, if for example a cable installation is being assessed, then one

cable has to be installed in one weather window, thus the fraction of time that cannot be used is considered as “lost time” and goes into weather downtime statistics.

Figure 3. Illustration of the working principle of the three different methods for WDT assessment

Note that DNV’s standard DNV-ST-N001, distinguishes two different operational times, whose sum is termed the reference period T_R :

$$T_R = T_{POP} + T_C \quad (8)$$

Where, T_{POP} is the planned operation period, and T_C is the estimated maximum contingency time. Therefore, this has to be accounted for when estimating the weather windows.

The above methods for weather assessment are sufficient for most operations, and especially in the planning phase and preliminary assessments when the exact vessel is not yet known (important for contracting purposes). However, some offshore operations characterised by high risks (e.g. in the Oil & Gas industry) may require a much more detailed assessment, as studied by Clades (2018), where a vessels dynamics were considered.

The ultimate method of WDT assessment for a complex project would be to simulate the installation programme by considering full environmental data (metocean parameter’s magnitude and directionality, and wave-current interaction effects), the vessel’s response to weather in time (considering the orientation), the dynamic positioning (DP) capability of the vessel, and the stochastic nature of the activity net duration (which can be represented with a normal distribution function as in the work of Ballard and Evans (2014)). However, this task would require much effort, and would hardly be justifiable, especially in the early project phases.

The present work is concentrated on the first two methods of WDT assessment, with a proposal of accounting for “waiting on current” time in the weather windows approach. The naming convention as presented by Rip (2015) and Lambkin et al. (2019) is followed in this work.

4 ASSESSMENT

An in-house tool, known as “GDG-WDAT, was developed mainly based on principles described in the work of Lambkin et al (2019). The output of the “GDG-WDAT” tool can be

used for estimating repetitive tasks, for example, the downtime of a cable installation operation.

The results of the joint probability distribution/wave scatter method (in terms of exceedance and non-exceedance probabilities) may be used for WDT estimation of a repetitive operation as presented by Graham (1982), while the implementation of the results of the empirical persistency distribution (weather windows) method are discussed by Hudson (2019).

The application of the results of a joint probability distribution method is much more straightforward for continuous operations, such as surveys or dredging, as the percentage of unfavourable weather is directly representative of the weather downtime (non-workable time).

The results of the empirical persistency distribution (weather windows) method in terms of monthly percentages of unfavourable weather is also directly representative of the weather downtime (non-workable time) for operations such as survey or personnel transfer activities using Crew Transfer Vessels (CTV’s).

On the other hand, estimating the WDT of an operation with a distinguished sequence of activities (lifting, or even cable installation) presents a bigger challenge as the results of the first two methods need to be applied to each activity separately (as each activity can have its own operational limits), as for example presented by Graham (1982). However, the validity of adding up the WDT obtained by different weather windows statistics for different activities is doubtful due to the requirement of performing the activities in sequence. For a more detailed insight in the WDT of these types of operations it is therefore advisable to use the simulation based methods.

Another important consideration is how to estimate the effects of a steady current on the WDT assessment, as it depends on the nature of an operation. This topic has not been covered in any of the referenced works. Here, two different operational situations are distinguished and methods of accounting for the steady currents are given for:

- Operations that have to be performed only when the current is below certain limits, e.g. operations with a remotely operated vehicle (ROV), or deployment and recovery of drilling pipe for offshore geotechnical investigations. In these cases the weather windows are driven by the current conditions. This effect is illustrated in Figure 4, binary sequence “B”, where it can be seen that the current is “breaking” the available weather window and thus reducing the workability significantly.
- Operations that can continue only when the current is below a given limit, but may be “on hold” when the currents are above the limit, e.g. a cable installation vessel’s DP system is generally unable to keep the required tolerance in currents higher than 1.5 m/s, in which case the operations stop, and the vessel will weathervane to remain in position, waiting for the current to reduce to continue cable laying. In this case, time will be lost (added to the WDT) for waiting on current periods, but the weather window will be determined by other parameters

Figure 4. Illustrative example of the current effect

(e.g. wind speed and wave height) and may still be used. This is illustrated in Figure 4, binary sequence “A”, where the vessel can wait on the current to decrease while still using the same weather window determined by H_s .

The second situation implies that “waiting on current” may be accounted for in the WDT assessment by first looking at the currents. The percentage of time that the current is above the operational limit can be identified and used to increase the required weather window. This new weather window can then be used as reference period in WDT assessment, and the results can be used to calculate the weather downtime.

5 CASE STUDY

To demonstrate the capability of the GDG-WDAT tool, a case study is presented in this section. The chosen metocean point is located 51.75 N, -6.75 E, see Figure 5. Data for winds and waves were extracted for the period between 1 January 1979 and 24 March 2022.

Other metocean parameters were not available and thus were not considered. The assumed limiting conditions for a hypothetical vessel are assumed to be 15 m/s wind speed and 2.0 m significant wave height. The results of the statistical analysis can be presented in several ways. The “GDG-WDAT” tool has the option to provide results in different formats.

Figure 5. Location of the metocean point used in this case study <https://www.findlatitudeandlongitude.com/>

Figure 6. Non-Exceedance plot for all years

Figure 6. Persistence (below) plot for reference period 48hrs

The difference from non-exceedance (joint probability method) and persistence (weather windows) can be observed from Figure 6 and 7, from which it can be observed that the workability (percentage of time the weather is below certain limits) is noticeably lower for persistence as it requires to have favourable weather for a number of consecutive hours.

The data presented on Figure 6 and 7 can also be represented as an empirical cumulative distribution function (ECDF) as presented on Figure 8 and Figure 9. It is clearly observed from Figure 9 how larger reference periods are rarer, and thus the workability reduces. The same data can be presented as a histogram, ECDF or in tables for monthly statistics, as per Figures 11 to 13. Finally, the histogram of non-exceedance (Figure 10), or persistence, presents a convenient way for fast identification of the most favourable periods of the year to start the operations.

Figure 65. Non-exceedance plot for all years

Figure 8. Persistence plot for each year (overlapping)

Figure 9. Non-exceedance plot for each month, all years (overlapping)

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
P0	0.8	0.0	15.7	41.1	51.6	64.4	54.6	48.1	50.6	23.8	11.3	0.8
P50	23.3	29.9	45.7	73.1	79.8	87.2	87.6	85.6	73.1	52.5	40.4	28.5
P80	48.6	50.6	59.8	84.5	89.4	92.8	94.3	92.9	83.2	61.9	56.2	41.9
P100	64.4	81.1	89.1	94.6	97.7	98.1	100	100	100	89.7	79.6	69.6

Figure 10. Non-exceedance for each month

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
P0	0.0	0.0	10.3	37.6	47.4	63.3	47.7	39.7	37.4	20.8	7.2	0.0
P50	18.1	24.7	39.4	70.6	77.0	85.1	87.0	83.9	69.0	47.5	34.5	24.2
P80	44.1	47.4	55.0	83.2	89.2	91.6	93.2	91.9	82.1	57.7	48.9	38.2
P100	59.5	73.8	88.7	94.6	97.7	98.1	100	100	100	89.2	74.2	62.8

Figure 11. Persistence (below) table for each month (numbered 1 to 12) and different P-values for a period of 24hrs (overlapping)

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
P0	0.0	0.0	9.0	31.7	44.0	54.6	39.9	32.4	31.4	14.7	3.3	0.0
P50	16.3	23.6	35.5	63.0	71.6	79.9	83.7	79.3	62.3	40.9	29.1	19.4
P80	35.7	37.9	50.3	77.0	83.1	88.0	91.2	87.9	77.7	49.9	39.9	30.7
P100	54.8	60.7	84.5	90.6	97.6	97.9	100	100	100	83.3	67.1	55.5

Figure 12. Persistence (below) table for each month (numbered 1 to 12) and different P-values for a period of 24hrs (non-overlapping)

The gross operational time T_T can be defined as the sum of the net operational time T_{NET} and the weather downtime T_{WDT} :

$$T_T = T_{NET} + T_{WDT} \quad (9)$$

The gross operational time may be obtained by using the results obtained by the “GDG-WDAT” tool as:

$$T_T = T_{NET}/P \quad (10)$$

Where P is the probability that the weather will be below the given limit obtained from the WDT analysis. The weather downtime can then be obtained from Equation (2).

For this example, assuming a net operational time of 24hrs, the gross operational time for a P50 value and the month of June, would be 27.5hrs, 28.2hrs and 30hrs, by using the values from Figures 11, 12 and 13, respectively. This would imply 3.5hrs, 4.2hrs and 6.0hrs weather downtime obtained from different statistics, from which it can be noted that, as expected, the first method results with lower WDT estimates than the persistence (weather windows) method. The example also shows the effect of increased WDT for the non-overlapping persistence probability – this difference may be more, or less pronounced, depending on the particular case and weather data.

6 CONCLUSION

Information about potential weather downtime (WDT) is essential for appropriate planning and costing of the offshore works. The problem of estimating weather downtime dates to the late 1960’s. In the early days, the challenge was to obtain sufficient data for a meaningful statistical analysis. However, with recent advances in weather modelling and the possibility of creating hindcast time series for many years (e.g. ERA5 data base being publicly available), the focus is switching to using this advantage in creating more sophisticated models for WDT assessment. Furthermore, historical data are now more easily available since the emergence of satellite-based wave measurements.

In this paper, three different methods of WDT assessment were briefly presented and explained, and a discussion on the effect of steady currents on estimating WDT is provided. In general, it can be concluded that the first two methods of WDT assessment are more straightforward to implement, but implementing the results for estimating WDT of operations like geotechnical surveys and cable installation is not so intuitive. On the other hand, implementing the simulation based method is significantly more demanding, but the results can be more readily used and understood.

To investigate the magnitude of weather downtime potential, an in-house innovative tool named “GDG-WDAT” has been developed, that can automatically download the ERA 5 weather data and use it for statistical analysis. A case study was presented to show some of the output capabilities of the tool. The tool is being enhanced to include the simulation based method, that has the possibility of accounting for waiting on current time.

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A novel approach to offshore site investigation using Distributed Acoustic Sensing

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ABSTRACT:

Offshore geophysical assessment is often characterised by the rapid collection of sub bottom profile data using various acoustic sources. This approach is invaluable in the provision of large datasets profiling offshore sediments, but has the major drawback of not determining their physical properties. More recently the application of UMASW to determine geotechnical properties of offshore sediments has provided the offshore developer with a more useful tool to assess the geotechnical properties of the sub surface. This approach is time consuming and where weather downtime is a key factor in the progress of an offshore investigation program resulting in a more sparse data coverage than would be ideal.

The purpose of this paper is to introduce a new technology in the field of offshore geotechnical investigation. Distributed Acoustic Sensing (DAS) is a method that utilises fibre optic cables as continuous sensing elements, measuring very small strain imposed on the glass core by the transmission of acoustic energy along the sea bed / water interface. One of the potential benefits of this over traditional sediment profiling methods is the rapid data acquisition over large scale deployed arrays. The shear wave data resolved from this approach is related directly to the small strain shear modulus G_{max} , which is a critical input parameter for static and dynamic foundation analysis. As well as providing detailed information for the design of offshore foundations the potential to deploy extensive linear arrays make the proposed methodology ideal for the assessment of linear investigations such as transmission cable route options. This paper presents data from differing geological settings, acquired as part of a recently completed SFI/iCRAG funded project.

KEY WORDS: Offshore Wind; Shear Wave Velocity; Geotechnical; Fibre Optic; Distributed Acoustic Sensing

7 INTRODUCTION

Offshore wind is a fundamental part of our plans for a green energy future. Reducing the Levelised Cost of Electricity (LCOE) is important for ensuring the future sustainability of wind energy (Razaei et al. 2018, Byrne et al. 2019, Byrne 2020). The application of more cost effective and less conservative geotechnical engineering is essential to the longer-term sustainability of the industry (Byrne 2020, Eiksund et al. 2014). Engineers, however, often have to resort to conservative designs due to a lack of available subsurface information (Muir Wood & Knight 2013). Current best practice for the characterisation of geotechnical properties of shallow marine sediments typically involves shallow seismic investigations and the subsequent collection of targeted borehole and / or Cone Penetration Test (CPT) data (Barwise et al. 2014). This approach requires multiple phases of high-cost survey work, with potentially low acquisition rates of sparse data, requiring technical integration that has limitations for design.

Over recent years, there has been increased recognition from the geotechnical industry on the use of geophysical properties when designing these structures (Eiksund et al. 2014, Rushton & Nguyen 2020, Lunne et al. 2013, Long et al. 2020). It is generally accepted that the dynamic loading applied to establish the natural frequency of the structure induces very small displacements (Prendergast et al. 2015). Therefore, the small-strain stiffness of the soil can be used to model soil displacements and is recognized as a key parameter when designing these dynamically sensitive structures (Eiksund et al. 2014, Prendergast et al. 2015, Versteijlen 2014). The seismic shear wave velocity (V_s) is related, through elastic theory, to the small strain shear modulus G_{max} , which is a critical input parameter for several engineering applications, including static and dynamic analysis of offshore foundation systems. Its measurement has, therefore, been recommended as standard practice for offshore site investigations in order to reduce design uncertainty (Lunne et al. 2013).

In this study, we developed an approach for rapid acquisition of spatially extensive V_s data based on Distributed Acoustic Sensing (DAS) of fibre optic cables laid on the seabed (Trafford et al. 2021, 2022). Using this approach, standard telecommunication optical fibres are interrogated by transmitting a light pulse and analysing the backscatter from microstructural variations naturally present within the fibre (Nickès & Ravet 2010). This effect is dominated primarily by elastic Rayleigh backscatter with c.0.1% of the backscattered light captured by the fibre and returned to the interrogator unit for analysis (Healey 1987).

Scholte waves propagate at the water-solid seabed interface and are different to Rayleigh waves propagating at the free surface, with the velocity variations related to the wavelength to water depth ratio (Kugler et al. 2005, 2007, Park et al. 2005). Sub seabed V_s profiles can be generated by inverting DAS derived seismic Scholte wave dispersion data.

This paper summarises a 3 year research project focussed on the use of DAS for offshore site investigations. In order to achieve this aim work was carried out at 3 test sites:

1. Blessington sand and gravel extraction site, County Wicklow (terrestrial),
2. Dollymount Strand, Dublin (Intertidal)
3. Dundalk Bay, N. Irish Sea.

The findings from each site are discussed in chronological order.

8 DISTRIBUTED ACOUSTIC SENSING (DAS)

Distributed sensing works by transmitting a pulse of coherent optical laser signal through a single mode fibre optic cable and measuring the variations in the naturally backscattered light (Nickès & Ravet 2010) from microscopic variations in the glass core, due to strain changes.

Figure 1 DAS waterfall plot from Blessington site showing A) 5 minute portion of data with active shots (horizontal lines) and noise generated by walking between stations (sloping noise). B) shows a single extracted shot and the conversion to a standard time series shot gather (C).

The phase of Rayleigh backscattered light along an optical fibre is well suited for monitoring dynamic strain changes, with a high spatial and temporal resolution. The application of this approach for measuring ground motion / seismic waves is called Distributed Acoustic Sensing (DAS). Current technologies are capable of resolving nano-strain induced by ground deformations from the interaction of acoustic waves with the fibre-optic cable (Jousset, et al. 2018, Masoudi, & Newson 2017).

Assessment of the DAS data is carried out using a Frequency Bandwidth Extracted (FBE) waterfall plot which is used to

monitor the recorded data in real time. This real time depiction is generated by applying a Fast Fourier Transform to full bandwidth data and displaying the summed energy as a colour intensity plot for each channel. Examples of waterfall plots can be seen in Figure 1. All the collected data were acquired using an OptaSense ODH4 laser interrogator system linked to industry standard fibre optic cables.

9 MULTICHANNEL ANALYSIS OF SURFACE WAVES

Multichannel Analysis of Surface Waves (MASW) is a technique that involves measuring dispersive waves travelling through the subsurface and converting these into shear wave velocity (V_s) profiles. Park et al. (1999). The dispersive waveforms travel at different velocities / frequencies combinations controlled by the stiffness profile of the ground.

Different frequency components of the generated surface wave travel at velocities relating to the stiffness of the subsurface according to their individual wavelength. The recorded data are converted to the phase velocity – frequency domain which defines the frequency characteristics of the propagating surface waves. The dispersion curves are picked and mathematically inverted to provide 1D vertical V_s profiles.

The data were analysed using both Surfseis and the Dinver module of the Geopsy open source software. Figure 2 shows the processing flow from shot gather to dispersion curve imaging to modelled V_s inversion. The analysis using the Monte Carlo method (Wathelet et al. 2004, 2008), has the benefit over the Surfseis inversion method (least squares approach) by giving a tangible assessment of the increasing level of uncertainty with increasing depth (increasing wavelength).

Figure 2: Data processing flow of DAS derived shot gather. a) 200 trace shot gather, b) dispersion curve image and c) modelled inversion of shear wave velocity.

10 BLESSINGTON SAND AND GRAVEL QUARRY

The first phase of the study was carried out at Blessington Quarry, a sand and gravel extraction site in County Wicklow, Figure 3. The trial site was chosen due to a relatively well documented geological setting, on site exposures as well favourable access considerations. The expected geology consists of medium dense bedded silts/sands over glacial till.

These glacial tills were anticipated to provide a vertical contrast in the mechanical properties of the deposits.

Figure 3: Location plan showing the Blessington site and the 100m long deployed fibre optic cable position

10.1 Investigation Methodology

The interrogator unit housed in a survey vehicle and powered by a portable generator. A 100m long fibre optic cable was deployed within a shallow trench and backfilled with sand to improve coupling. The DAS system was configured to acquire data using a 2m gauge length with 1m channel spacing. The gauge length is the length of fibre over which the backscattered light is averaged to measure the induced strain.

Seismic data were recorded with both the DAS system and a Geonics 24 channel seismograph for validation of the results.

4.5Hz vertical geophones with variable spacing were used with the seismograph to allow comparisons at different source / receiver geometries. A sledgehammer and plate was used as the source with an inertia trigger mechanism to give an identical timestamp on both sets of seismic data.

Figure 4. Processing flow of seismic data. geophone (A) and DAS (C) shot gathers are converted to phase velocity –

frequency plots (B and D) to compare the surface wave response of each.

10.2 Comparison Seismic Data Acquisition

The composite shot record, Figure 4A, was created by combining the data from 1, 2 and 4m geophone spacing to compare the vertical ground displacement response of the geophone sensor to the inline strain response of the fibre optic cable. The phase velocity – frequency plots (Figure 4 (B and D)) show an identical response from both the geophone and DAS datasets.

10.3 Blessington Summary

The findings from this phase of the study showed that it was possible to collect DAS data with suitable geometry for the use in surface wave analysis for engineering applications. Where DAS may become increasingly useful is in the ability to continuously record, and therefore monitor, ground conditions over significant distances not feasible from the use of other currently available technologies.

11 DOLLYMOUNT STRAND, COUNTY DUBLIN

Following on from the work carried out at Blessington, trials were carried out at Dollymount Strand (Figure 5), County Dublin. This work is discussed in more detail in Trafford et al. (2021).

Figure 5: Location plan showing Dollymount Strand and the 1km long deployed fibre optic cable position

The location was chosen as a test site, prior to full offshore testing, due to the shallow sloping beach resulting in a wide intertidal zone with few sand bars to form obstructions to nearshore access by small survey craft.

11.1 Investigation Methodology

The interrogator unit was housed in a survey vehicle at the beach head. A 1000m long fibre optic cable was deployed perpendicular to the shoreline, at high tide, using a small landing craft (Figure 6b). The DAS system was configured to acquire data using a 2m gauge length with 1m channel

spacing, effectively creating over 900 active channels spanning the beach, intertidal and marine zones (Figure 7). In this configuration the system is capable of acquiring up to 5km of data.

Figure 6: Survey vehicles / vessels used for the study. a) Interrogator unit housed in van at beach head above high water mark. b) "landing craft" used to deliver and deploy cable (adapted from Trafford 2021).

Figure 7: Schematic setup showing survey procedures at high and low water (adapted from Trafford 2021).

A 24 channel Geometrics DHA-7 hydrophone cable with 3.125m channel spacing was deployed alongside the DAS cable in the nearshore zone to allow a direct comparison between the 2 sensor types. A 9m Rigid Hull Inflatable Boat (RHIB) was used as the source vessel (Figure 8), operating a 12 cu in Sercel Mini G Airgun with a radio link to timestamp the DAS data with the T_0 trigger when the airgun was fired, whilst simultaneously triggering the seismograph when collecting hydrophone shot gathers.

Figure 8: 9m Rigid Hull Inflatable Boat (RHIB) used to operate and position seismic source.

In order to survive the stresses of a dynamic marine environment, as well as the strain exerted during deployment, an industry standard Corrugated Steel Tape (CST) armoured loose tube cable was chosen to trial the proposed methodology.

The FBE data presented in Figure 9a (frequency band 5 to 55Hz) represents a 20 minute portion of the recorded DAS data containing 20 airgun records (horizontal events) at different points along the cable.

Figure 9: Waterfall plots; a) 20 minute record showing individual shots (horizontal) and propagating ocean waves (sloping). b) 30 second record showing full cable length with mid shot and c) 5 second ‘shot’ record showing Scholte wave propagating 500m (adapted from Trafford 2021).

100 and 200 trace shot gathers were extracted from the DAS data to produce 1D V_s profiles at c. 25m intervals along the length of the fibre optic cable. The 1D profiles were combined to produce a 2D V_s profile between the seabed and c. 20m depth. Figure 2 shows the processing flow of a 200 trace extracted shot gather with the numerically modelled inversion using the Monte-Carlo method.

11.2 Comparison Source / Environment Conditions

By surveying across the full tidal range it was possible to collect data at the same exact location using three different sensor types:

- 1) Distributed Acoustic Sensing with fibre optic cable with airgun source at high water
- 2) Hydrophone cable with airgun at high water
- 3) Geophones with hammer/plate source at low water

Figure 10 shows comparison Rayleigh wave phase velocity (V_{ph}) – frequency (f) plots for the different sensor types with

the response of Scholte waves collected in the marine setting at high water compared to Rayleigh waves collected on the ‘dry’ beach at low water. The $V_{ph} - f$ plots show high levels of consistency between the different acquisition methodologies.

Figure 10: Comparison dispersion curve images. a) and b) were collected with geophones and fibre optic cable respectively, at low tide using a sledgehammer source. c) and d) were collected with fibre cable and hydrophones respectively, at high tide using an airgun source in c. 3m water depth (adapted from Trafford 2021).

11.3 Dollymount Summary

The findings from the Dollymount Strand phase of the study highlighted that the methodology was scalable with the potential to collect data from up to 5km of fibre optic cable from a single deployment. The collected data were validated against other commonly used geophysical methods showing a highly comparable response from the fibre compared to hydrophones and geophones.

As well as resolving the active shot records the system was also found to be sensitive to the pressure changes associated

with the propagation of ocean waves which would indicate the potential of DAS in the assessment of seabed stress variations associated with tide and wave action.

DUNDALK BAY, IRISH SEA

The trial sites within Dundalk Bay were chosen at locations where previous geotechnical and geophysical data was available. This was essential in order to validate the findings from the DAS survey against industry standard assessments. This work is discussed in more detail in Trafford et al. (2022).

The locations spanned differing seabed conditions with thick sequences of very soft clay/silts known as the Western Irish Sea Mud Belt (Coughlan et al. 2019) (Site 1), to the south and areas of shallow glacial deposits, including glacial till (Site 2), to the north, in water depths between c. 20 and 50 m (Figure 11).

Figure 11. Location plan showing test sites 1 and 2 overlaid on bathymetry data. MBES and sediment classification data is Irish Public Sector Data (INFOMAR) licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0) licence and accessed through <https://www.infomar.ie>.

The survey setup was similar to that used at Dollymount Strand apart from the RV Celtic Voyager being used as the acquisition platform. The Interrogator Unit was housed within the dry lab on board the Voyager with a 1000m long (CST) armoured fibre optic cable being deployed by the RIB at several sites corresponding with previous CPT locations. USBL transponders were also attached to the cable to give real time positions of the cable ends and aid in the positioning of the gun boat in close proximity to the cable on the seabed (Figure 12).

Processing flows for data acquired at Sites 1 and 2 in the Dundalk Bay area are provided in Figure 13. The multichannel shot gathers were muted (Figure 13 a,e), before

being converted to a dispersion image using a 2D wave field-transformation method. McMechan & Yedlin (1981), Park et al. (1999). Dispersion curves were picked from the resulting frequency-phase velocity images (Figure 13 b,f) and extracted for inversion to produce a 1D V_s -depth profile using a Monte-Carlo approach (Wathelet et al. 2004, 2008), (Figure 13 c,g).

Figure 12. Schematic view of deployment methodology overlaid on high resolution sparker reflection data (Not To Scale).

Figure 13. Processed data from sites 1 and 2 showing the response from the thick muds compared to the shallow sands/tills with the corresponding CPT results.

Sub-bottom profiling is effective at determining acoustic layering but one of the limitations is the lack of velocity information relating to stiffness/density profiling. The lowest layer resolved in a sub-bottom profile section is often referred to as the acoustic basement and ideally would represent the top of bedrock but often this is not the case. By combining the sub bottom profile data with the DAS derived V_s profiles, it is possible to better understand the geological layering, while also enabling interpretation of the small strain shear stiffness, G_{max} .

In this case, DAS derived V_s profiling from Site 1, would indicate that the acoustic basement represents the transition from marine sediments to stiff glacial material rather than bedrock (Figure 14).

Figure 14. 2D Shear Wave velocity profile (colour scale image) and CPT cone resistance, qt (red line graph) overlaid on high resolution sparker reflection data (pseudo grey scale image) from Site 1.

12 CONCLUSION

The study has shown that DAS is an effective approach to collecting both land and marine surface wave data and as such is an ideal method for the assessment of sites destined for the development of offshore renewables.

The real benefits of DAS for offshore investigations are in its ability to offer extensive sensor lengths from single cable deployments and the generation of detailed 2D shear wave profiles. The associated reduction in deployment and survey duration is particularly important when working in the marine environment due to potentially short and expensive weather windows.

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A Review of Anchoring Solutions for Offshore Wind Turbines

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ABSTRACT: Ambitious targets have been set for offshore wind generation by countries aiming to reduce carbon emissions. Floating wind farms are an essential component of the wind energy industry, as wind turbines grow bigger and are placed in deeper waters. Mooring and anchoring systems are key to the stability of floating offshore wind turbines (OWT). Anchoring solutions have to be tailored for seabed conditions and mooring loads. Unlike oil and gas rigs, wind turbines are installed in arrays, that may facilitate an optimised sharing of anchors. The design of a mooring system for floating OWTs also requires consideration of the serviceability limit states of the delicate tower-rotor-nacelle assembly. In this paper, we discuss the various anchoring solutions for floating OWTs emphasising their geotechnical design and installation processes.

KEY WORDS: Floating offshore wind turbine, marine anchor, wind turbine foundation.

1 INTRODUCTION

Wind power is expected to become the cheapest form of green energy, with rapid expansion and reducing installation and operating costs. Ambitious targets set by the EU towards the 2030 climate target plan call for increasing the contribution from offshore wind sector to at least 60 GW by 2030 (European Commission, 2020). For example, the target set by Ireland for 2030 is 5 GW from offshore wind farms (Department of Transport, Government of Ireland, 2021), which will require large scale infrastructure mobilization. Offshore wind comes with certain advantages over onshore wind, such as less disturbance on local communities, minimal hassle in transportation and installation, and higher wind speeds. Technological advances in turbine design, blade design, wind prediction, and foundation system continue to enable bigger OWTs in deeper waters.

The foundation is a key component of an OWT, typically costing between 25 and 34 % of the total cost. Offshore wind turbines can be broadly divided into either fixed-bottom systems or floating systems. Fixed systems are generally adopted for water depths of up to 70 m. Examples of fixed offshore wind substructures include monopiles, gravity bases, and tripods or jackets supported on piles or suction caissons. For water depths beyond 70 m, floating wind turbines anchored to the seabed by a mooring system are adopted. Apart from water depth, the selection of a foundation system can also be influenced by factors such as seabed conditions, turbine characteristics and economics. The Irish Sea is reported to have conditions conducive to both fixed and floating offshore wind turbines (Coughlan et al., 2020). However, the larger Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ) has deeper seabed levels as can be seen from the Bathymetry Map in Fig 1. Floating wind turbines also have a low seabed footprint and have the advantage of easy installation, maintenance and decommissioning.

Figure 1. Visualisation of Bathymetry data around Ireland (EMODnet Bathymetry Consortium, 2020).

Anchoring systems of varying types are employed to anchor and stabilise floating OWTs. The wind turbine structure, being dynamically sensitive, requires a carefully designed

substructure, accounting for fatigue effects across the intended life cycle.

Without doubt, floating offshore structures and anchoring technologies are poised to play a crucial role in wind farms of the future. In this paper, we present a review of existing anchoring solutions for offshore wind turbines, their geotechnical design challenges, and some of the latest developments.

2 FLOATING WIND TURBINES

2.1 Structural Design

Regardless of their fundamental differences, the floating offshore wind energy industry has widely adopted technology from deep water oil and gas industry. There are at present, over 80 different concepts of floating OWTs (Butterfield et al., 2007). However, they can be categorized in three main groups:

- Tension Leg Platform (TLP): Floating system stabilized by tensioned mooring
- Spar buoy concept: Floating system consists of a ballast stabilized deep cylindrical base
- Semi-submersible type: Free-surface stabilized structures with a relatively small draft

The three types of floating wind turbines are presented in Figure 2. Each type has its own advantages and disadvantages. The TLP, for example, has excellent stability but relies on high loads on the mooring and anchoring system. It also involves a complex installation procedure that needs an installation barge. The spar buoy type also provides excellent stability but is restricted for use in deep water locations. Its large draft makes it difficult to tow the structure to and from a port. The semi-submersible type is by far the most popular owing to its low draft and operability in shallow waters. It can be fabricated onshore and towed to place using tugboats.

Figure 2. Illustration showing the types of floating wind turbine.

The first test floating OWT was an 80 kW turbine on a TLP system installed off the Italian coast by Blue H Technologies in 2008 (González & Diaz-Casas, 2016). The first MW scale floating wind turbine was the Hywind turbine in the North Sea with 2.3 MW turbine supported by a spar buoy type substructure, installed in 2009 (Skaare et al., 2015). The

follow up 30 MW Hywind Scotland pilot park includes five 6 MW floating turbines supported on spar buoy substructures. Another development was the 2 MW WindFloat semi-submersible floating concept off the coast of Portugal launched in 2011 (González & Diaz-Casas, 2016). Following up from this, the Windfloat Atlantic project in Portugal and Windfloat Kincardine project in Scotland were recently developed using the same semi-submersible technology with 8.4 and 9.5 MW turbines respectively.

The design of a floating OWT is a collaborative effort between the turbine manufacturer, structural designer, and the foundation designer. The structure of an OWT can be categorized as a high slenderness-low stiffness dynamical system. The modes of vibration of a floating OWT include heave, surge, sway, roll bending and pitch bending modes. A collection of simplified formulae to estimate the natural frequency of floating OWTs can be found in Varghese et al. (2022).

2.2 Mooring Configurations

The most common mooring configurations for offshore wind turbines are catenary mooring (for semi-submersible and spar buoy types) and taut leg mooring for TLPs. Figure 3 shows the mooring line configurations in a spar buoy type floating OWT. The catenary mooring system with a large footprint, consists of a line profile with part of the mooring line lying on the seabed in a static equilibrium position. The catenary shape of the mooring line provides the necessary compliance to the floating systems static offset and dynamic motions. Taut leg mooring systems have mooring lines taut from the fairlead on the floater to the anchor at the seabed. The compliance to static offset and dynamic response of the floater is mainly from the mooring line tensile stretch (Ma et al., 2019). There

are also semi taut mooring systems with a typical loading angle of 45° at the anchor point. This type of mooring system would have a medium footprint on the seabed.

Floating OWTs may be deployed in arrays covering a wide areal extend. Some researchers suggest that significant cost savings may be achieved by attaching more than one mooring line to a seabed anchor. This ‘multiline’ concept can not only save installation cost, but also reduces the cost of offshore geotechnical investigations (Diaz et al., 2016). As an example Fontana et al. (2016) showed that for a wind farm with three mooring lines attached to a single anchor, the multiline concept would reduce the number of anchors by 67 %. They calculated that, depending on the farm layout and depth of seabed, the anchor reductions can be in the range of 33 to 84 %.

3 SUBSEA ANCHORING SYSTEMS

Moored floating structures exert a variety of loads to the anchoring system. The catenary system can apply horizontal loads, the semi-taut system may apply a combination of horizontal and vertical loads, while the taut leg system can apply vertical loads. The anchor type is often seabed specific, and a comprehensive analysis often precedes its choice. The common anchoring systems employed by the offshore industry are:

- Dead weight anchor
- Driven pile anchor
- Suction pile anchor
- Drag anchor
- Embedded plate anchor

Figure 4 shows the various anchoring systems that are commonly used in floating wind farms. The geotechnical

Figure 3: Normal operating conditions and stretched mooring line configurations (adapted from Arany and Bhattacharya, 2018)

design of an anchor involves determination of its size and depth of embedment and the ability of the anchor to achieve the required embedment depth. One of the first detailed discussion on the type and size of anchors for offshore structures can be found in Taylor (1982).

The limit states for the design of offshore wind turbine anchors can be classified as ultimate limit states (ULS), service limit states (SLS) and fatigue limit states (FLS). The ULS considers factors such as :

- Geotechnical failure in overturning, sliding and uplift
- Loss of structural resistance leading to plastic hinge or cracks in the material
- Failure in components such a connections and mooring lines

The SLS correspond to tolerance criteria for:

- Excessive displacements, rotations, or vibration amplitudes over the design life.
- Differential settlement of anchors

Fatigue limit states corresponds to long term cyclic stresses and deformations that can lead to a failure of the anchor. A review of the various types of anchors for floating OWTs are presented below.

Figure 4. Illustration showing the types of anchor systems for floating OWTs.

3.1 Dead weight anchor

Dead weight anchors rely on their weight to resist vertical loads and the sliding friction to resist lateral loads. Their design involves calculation of the holding capacity of the seabed, as well as the buoyant weight to resist sliding (VanZwieten Jr et al., 2014). Dead weight anchors can also be designed with shear keys to increase the lateral sliding capacity. However, the large size and weight of these anchors can increase the installation costs. They are also difficult to remove upon decommissioning.

3.2 Driven pile anchor

Driven pile anchors are a well-established technology that has been used widely in onshore and offshore energy systems. Driven piles are compatible with any loading angle, and can be installed in soil profiles ranging from soft clay to soft rock (Vijayvergiya et al., 1977). However, on major drawback of driven pile anchor is the complex installation procedure requiring specialist vessels. Also installation of several hundreds of pile anchors for a large offshore wind farm could result in environmentally unacceptable noise levels (Ainslie et al., 2012; Tsouvalas, 2020). However, there are technologies by which noise levels can be minimised such as 1) the use of bubble curtains to attenuate acoustical waves (Reimann & Grabe, 2015; Würsig et al., 2000), 2) the use of underwater jetting (Zakeri et al., 2014) or 3) hydraulic jacked-in piling system (Lwti et al., 2021). Different piling techniques have also been proposed with examples including geosynthetic reinforcement, anchored piles with foldable anchors fitted to the sides (Jeong et al., 2020) and helical piles

3.3 Suction pile anchor

Suction piles are open ended low aspect ratio piles that are installed partially by self-weight and partially by inducing suction from a pumping mechanism. The optimal aspect ratios can be broadly identified for various soil types as (Aubeny, 2017):

- Dense sands: < 1.5
- Stiff clays: 1.5 to 3
- Soft clays: > 5

Installation of suction anchors in homogeneous clays and sands are more or less straight forward (K. H. Andersen et al., 2008; L. V. Andersen et al., 2012). Installation in stratified deposits however, requires procedures such as jetting and cycling (Tjelta, 2015). Suction piles or caissons can resist loads at any angle. The analysis methodology for ultimate capacity of suction piles under lateral and inclined loads are well established (Aubeny et al., 2003; Aubeny et al., 2001). The holding capacity of a suction caisson can be determined based on the envelop of vertical and horizontal load components at the anchor (Arany & Bhattacharya, 2018; Randolph & Gourvenec, 2017; Supachawarote et al., 2004). A recent study by Cheng et al. (2021) concluded that the pullout capacity and soil failure mechanism of a suction caisson is a function of the pad eye location. An increasing angle of loading (with the horizontal) was found to decrease the pullout capacity. Soil structure interaction studies by Esfeh & Kaynia (2019) found that earthquake induced liquefaction combined with static mooring loads can result in permanent tilt and displacements in suction piles. The Hywind Scotland floating wind project spar buoys are anchored with suction caissons.

3.4 Drag anchor

Drag anchors consists of a fluke (bearing plate) that is inserted into the seabed by dragging it with a chain or wire rope. The fluke is attached to the anchor line by a ‘shank’ which comprises of one or more plates. The fluke shank angle can be adjected such that soil failure occurs in a direction parallel to

the fluke and the anchor moves downward when dragged. The first commercial use of drag-in plate anchors can be traced back to 1998 (H. Liu et al., 2010). In stiff clays and sands the fluke-shank angle is typically around 30° as the penetration into the seabed is typically less than 1 to 2 fluke lengths (Ma et al., 2019). For soft clay beds the angle is typically set around 50°. In soft clay profiles that exhibit increasing strength with depth, higher penetration can lead to substantial uplift capacity (Thorne, 1998). Limit equilibrium based methods to estimate the capacity of drag anchors can be found in Dahlberg (1998) and Det Norske Veritas (2013). The major advantage of drag anchors is the ease of installation and proven performance. Drag anchors can be retrieved by increasing the tension to the estimated recovery loads. The recovery loads in cohesionless soils can be typically 20 to 30 % of the installation load (highest tension that the anchor was subjected to), while in clays this increases to between 80 and 100 % (Ma et al., 2019).

3.5 Embedded plate anchor

Embedded plate anchors or vertically loaded plate anchors (VPA) have been studied and applied since the 1970s. From early laboratory studies (Das, 1978; Vesić, 1971) to numerical studies (Khatri & Kumar, 2009; Merifield et al., 2001; Song et al., 2008), the short-term static capacity of plate anchors has been investigated in detail. When an uplift force is applied to an anchor, the soil above the plate experiences a compression while the soil below is relieved from stress. The associated decrease in pore water pressure below the anchor results in a suction called the mud suction force. The ultimate pullout capacity of plate anchors can be estimated using procedures laid out in studies such as Kame et al. (2012); J. Liu et al. (2018); Merifield & Sloan (2006); Yu et al. (2011). The holding capacity of plate anchors in a wide range of plate anchor geometries is also a well-studied topic (Martin & Randolph, 2001; Merifield et al., 2001; Song et al., 2008; Wang et al., 2010; Yu et al., 2011).

While the VPAs are mostly installed similar to drag anchors, the Suction Embedded Plate Anchor (SEPLA) is a system that combines the advantages of suction caissons and VPAs (Dove, 1998). The SEPLA employs a suction caisson to embed the plate anchor in position at a desired depth. The plate anchor mooring line is then disengaged from the caisson, and it is pulled up by reversing the pump flow direction. SEPLAs have been used extensively in oil and gas rigs (Wong et al., 2012). Another new technology similar to the SEPLA system is the dynamically embedded plate anchor (DEPLA). The DEPLA system consists of a rocket shaped anchor that penetrates to a required depth using kinetic energy from its free-fall and self-weight (Blake & O'Loughlin, 2012; Blake & O'Loughlin, 2015; O'Loughlin et al., 2013). The central shaft can be retrieved thereby placing the anchor at its position. A simplified design procedure for the DEPLA system can be found in O'Loughlin et al. (2016).

4 SUMMARY

Subsea anchors play an important role in stabilising floating offshore wind turbines. A review of the existing technologies for anchoring floating OWTs is presented in this paper. While most initial developments came from the oil and gas industry,

floating offshore wind farms present new challenges in terms of serviceability criteria for anchoring solutions. With the clean energy and sustainability being prime importance in the offshore wind industry, it becomes necessary to develop sustainable anchoring solutions with the least environmental impact.

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